

D4.1 Understanding Super Users' climate information requirements and decision-making context to inform the co-design of case study specifications

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* **R**=Document, report; **DEM**=Demonstrator, pilot, prototype; **DEC**=website, patent filings, videos, etc.; **OTHER**=other

** **PU**=Public, **CO**=Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services), **CI**=Classified

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Executive Summary

In this deliverable, we describe the decision-making context of each of the five Super Users of the ASPECT project. These key users are working closely with ASPECT climate services scientists in Work Package 4 so we can understand how the Super User does or could use climate information, how they make decisions, and how seamless climate information could be useful for decision making by the Super User. This deliverable provides important background information gathered by climate services scientists through various interviews or other interactions with Super Users. In addition, we identify decisions of interest for each Super User which climate prediction information could potentially support, as part of the co-design process of five ASPECT case studies. By design, the Super Users' needs are distinct from one another, with Super Users spanning different sectors of society. Climate service scientists within ASPECT are working together with the Super Users to co-produce climate service prototypes focusing on key decisions of interest aligned to the seamless nature of the ASPECT project. Initially, the climate service prototypes are being designed to use existing climate prediction and projection information, available prior to the ASPECT project.

At the end of each section about each Super User, we describe how the information collected for each Super User has informed the direction of the case study designs for the different Super Users. This provides key information for other scientific work-packages in the ASPECT project so that research in areas such as understanding skill of predictions, downscaling and temporal merging of climate information can be tailored toward the case studies. This enables other work-packages in the ASPECT consortium to provide useful scientific and user relevant outputs that, in future, can be incorporated into the enhanced climate service prototypes that will use novel outputs from the ASPECT project. Ultimately this will enable an assessment of the value and benefits of ASPECT developments for these case studies. This deliverable therefore provides important foundation knowledge that will contribute to objective 2 (assessing whether new extended forecasts can provide improved information for users), objective 3 (applying new seamless merging approaches to user-relevant adaptation decisions), and objective 5 (exploring how users can get value from seamless climate information for decision-making). The information about the Super Users decision-making context is also useful for ASPECT upscaling research, highlighting likely concerns of similar users and their sectors.

About ASPECT

ASPECT aims to set up and demonstrate a seamless climate information (SCI) system with a time horizon up to 30 years and accompanied with underlying research and using climate information for sectoral applications. The project's goal is to improve existing climate prediction systems and to merge their outputs across timescales together with climate projections to unify a SCI as a standard for sectoral decision-making.

The project focus will be on European climate information, but we will also look where there is a wider policy interest (e.g., disaster preparedness) and in regions of European interest. We will maintain a strong link with the WCRP lighthouse activities to exploit learning for explaining and predicting earth system change. To incorporate a diversity of information, the SCI system will be based on multi-model climate forecasts and will build on learning from projects such as EUCP. It will align with new activities on Digital Twins within Europe, including DestinE. The SCI will combine physical science aspects with those from other disciplines to ensure the information is robust, reliable, and relevant for a range of user-driven decision cases. The information package will incorporate baseline forecasts and projections (plus uncertainty), and will explore new frontiers (e.g., extremes which are of socioeconomic high-level interest).

To ensure success, the research will encompass: an understanding and attribution of various processes along timescales (such as exploring signal-to-noise ratio) and their impact on predictability, new ways of initialisation of the prediction systems, merging predictions with projections, provision of regional SCI for Europe by downscaling (statistical methods, AI) and HighRes models (including convection-permitting models) and innovative post-processing method enhancing the skill and robustness of the climate forecasts.

1 Introduction

In this report we share our understanding of our Super Users and their decision making, obtained through user engagement over the first 2 years of the project. The main objective was to understand each Super Users' decision making context and identify their information requirements for time scales ranging from the next season up to 30 years. We particularly focus on decisions across different time scales, as one of the main aims of the project is to bridge the gap between different prediction systems by providing seamless climate information. The project also aims to enhance the predictions for time scales at the interface between the different existing prediction systems, for which predictability is more limited and so is their value for decision making.

The first three Super Users from the project were involved at the proposal stage, and are from the agriculture (grape/wine), finance (pensions) and governance sectors (EU Mission on Climate Adaptation). Two additional Super Users were identified after a competition launched in June 2023. From the 13 applications received, two case studies, both from the humanitarian sector, were selected tackling different challenges, regions and decision types. One of the case studies focuses on disaster response planning during extreme events and the other anticipatory action for health, particularly targeting children's malnutrition. Figure 1 highlights the five sectors that the Super Users represent.

Figure 1. The sectors the ASPECT Super Users represent.

This report presents the needs of the ASPECT Super Users in a broad sense. Some of these needs for decision making are outlined in Figure 2, representing the spatial and temporal scales of decision making across the Super Users. However, not all the requests will be possible to meet by the project, either due to technical feasibility, time/resource limitations or because they fall outside of the project’s scope. Being transparent about opportunities and limitations throughout the project has helped manage the expectations of both providers and Super Users.

Figure 2. The decisions that the Super Users are interested in seamless climate information for.

Figure 3. The areas and timescales of focus for the case studies co-produced with each Super User.

Ultimately the engagement with the Super Users has led to particular decisions of interest to the Super Users being co-developed into appropriate case studies associated with each Super User. The case study areas of focus are outlined in Figure 3 and are briefly outlined below, with more information in following dedicated sections for each case study:

[Agriculture \(grape/wine\)](#) The wine case study (led by Barcelona Supercomputing Centre, 'BSC') is co-developing climate information at seasonal-to-decadal time scales to support two key decisions by Codorniu-Raimat: spring frost protection and water management.

[Finance \(pensions\)](#) The case study (led by the Met Office, 'MO') is being designed to leverage change in the financial sector across Europe and beyond, specifically to highlight the physical risk that pension funds may be carrying within their portfolios and present examples using European extreme rainfall data in a way that is persuasive to key actors in pension fund decision making.

[Governance \(EU Mission for climate adaptation\)](#) The case study (led by Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici, 'CMCC') focuses on the strategic use of climate knowledge for regional risk assessment and adaptation strategies, and creating enabling conditions for the development of regional climate resilience. For the pilot demonstration (the Emilia Romagna region) the case study will consider extreme heat affecting major urban centres and on intense convective precipitation events impacting the

low-altitude former floodplain areas, which are now developed for urban and agricultural purposes and depend on artificial drainage.

[Disaster response during extreme events](#) This case study (MO led) focuses on the increased frequency of heatwaves and hot summers in the future in the UK that might create a risk to future operations (e.g. where British Red Cross volunteers need to be recruited, where emergency vehicles should be located, and what protective equipment, medicines and workwear are most suitable), and will support funding applications for responding to future extreme heat events. In addition, combining information at longer 20-30 year timescales with vulnerability data will help to identify where pockets of risk are evolving as the climate changes.

[Humanitarian \(anticipatory action to prevent malnutrition\)](#) The case study (BSC led) will focus on how climate impacts (heatwaves and desertification on food production, disease outbreaks following flooding) affect the affordability of a nutritious diet, helping Save the Children with anticipatory action in African countries.

Each of these case studies, developed from the user engagement interactions in Work Package (henceforth 'WP') 4, are one of the key ways that the ASPECT project is working with users, and the information contained in this deliverable is important foundation information to inform the direction of work across the other work packages of the consortium (Figure 4). WP1, WP2 and WP3 are producing data and information of direct use to the case studies and the climate service prototype development in WP4, and which will be critical for the assessment of benefit of the new data and information to users (Figure 4). WP5 researches the scaling up of case study designs and WP6 will produce climate information delivery systems and WP7 communication outputs about the Super Users and the case studies (Figure 4). The user engagement by WP4 facilitates the flow of information from other work packages in the project, as well as the return flow of information to the consortium. The user engagement work with the Super User therefore contributes to the co-design of the research methodologies in several work packages, especially those for understanding predictability of specific variables or metrics (WP2), and for improving climate information through temporal merging and downscaling (WP3), in addition to the climate service prototype design (WP4). In addition, scientific and technical perspectives from across the consortium help WP4 in the co-design of the case study and the climate service prototypes with the Super Users.

Figure 4. The information workflow across the ASPECT project

2 General Approach

In-depth interviews and/or discussion formats have been selected as a general approach for the case studies because they allow for flexible, detailed, and bilateral or multilateral (for those involving a group of respondents) conversations between climate service teams and Super Users. Direct interactions easily allow perceiving which are key issues for the users and shaping the conversations case by case. Key common objectives for each case study included exploring the needs and motivations of Super Users regarding adaptation to climate change in the medium and long term, identifying Super User decisions that depend on future climate, exploring which decisions and adaptation measures are likely to have the greatest impact, and what might be the added value of seamless climate information compared to current existing climate information for the Super User. Whilst these common objectives in terms of what information to gather were set in advance to ensure the consistency of the information collected across the different case studies (resulting in an interaction guidance available in Annex I), the climate service teams were driving the conversation to the topics where each of the users was able to give a greater contribution, letting the conversation flow.

3 Agriculture (grape/wine sector)

3.1 Summary of Super User Decision Making Context

The discussion on topic-specific questions departed from the figure presented by Xavier Bordes (Codorniu Super User involved in ASPECT) during the project kick-off meeting (Figure 5), putting special attention to the decisions cutting across different time scales.

Figure 5. Wine decision-making processes at different timescales. Slide presented by Codorniu during the ASPECT kick-off meeting.

In general, the needs of the grape/wine sector are mainly related to seasonal and decadal time scales. The grapevine has a lifetime of around 25 years, hence climate information at longer time horizons is not relevant for the users from the wine industry (or at least **they could not see any difference in using predictions in 20- and 30-years' time**). This was one of the questions that WP1 was interested in defining.

Another potential improvement of the project (WP1) is the provision of **seasonal predictions up to 24 months** and updated every 6 months. The Super Users from Codorniu were asked about their interest in these predictions which would allow them to plan for 1 and 2 years ahead. No immediate need was identified by them, but they acknowledged that they were not thinking of using this information because it is not currently available. However, they could explore its potential usefulness in the frame of the project.

3.2 Introduction to the grape and wine sector

The wine sector is an important pillar of the global economy. Particularly, Europe is the world leader in producing, consuming, importing, and exporting wine ([European Commission, 2020](#)) and the wine market had a total value of €349.8 billion in 2021 ([Wine News, 2022](#)). In Catalonia, the wine industry represents the third agri-food sector, with an annual turnover close to €1.2 billion ([Prodeca, 2022](#)). Climate variations strongly affect the changes in the

year-to-year production of wine and grapes ([Cunha and Richter, 2012](#), [Santos *et al.* 2013](#)). This influence is due to the grapevine development requiring specific conditions of temperature, precipitation, humidity, and solar radiation ([Fraga *et al.* 2020](#)). In this context, reliable and timely information on climatic fluctuations will enable wineries to optimise the planning and management of activities over a range of timescales ([Fernández González *et al.* 2011](#), [Barriguiha *et al.* 2021](#)).

The ASPECT Super User for the agriculture sector is Codorniu-Raventós, which is the oldest wine company in Spain, with more than 470 years of history in the production of quality wines and cava. It has over 3,000 hectares of vineyards that are owned directly by the company or under its direct supervision, making them one of the largest vineyard owners in Europe. Their oenological expertise has led them to establish 15 wineries in some of the best winegrowing areas in the world and to have a sales presence in more than 50 countries.

3.3 Super User Meetings during 2023 and 2024

Engagement with the company Raimat-Codorniu from the grape and wine sector has been carried out by BSC. A scoping meeting between BSC and Codorniu took place during the proposal preparation, where the interest of the company in climate information cutting across different time scales was discussed. After ASPECT's kick-off in February 2023, which was also attended by Codorniu as a consortium partner, BSC visited Codorniu's premises in Raimat (Spain) for a joint meeting. During the meeting, the ASPECT project was presented in more detail by BSC, emphasising the potential benefits for Codorniu and, in turn, Codorniu presented the company and their day-to-day work, and described their familiarity with climate information acquired from their involvement in previous EU-funded projects, such as [VISCA](#)¹. This interaction was the starting point for understanding the Super User's needs and requirements, as well as their attitude towards probabilistic information and expectations regarding the project's results. As a result of this meeting, a set of specifications was gathered with information on the case study to be developed for the wine sector. These specifications aimed to share the information on user needs with the other WPs. After the first technical developments were made, other in-person meetings followed (one at the Codorniu-Raimat facilities in May 2024, and the other at BSC facilities in June 2024). These meetings were used to inform the Super User about the climate information being created and further tailor such information to increase its usability and salience for their decision-making processes. Interactions with the user were used to discuss how probabilistic information is produced and should be interpreted, as well as to present some preliminary results to Codorniu, compare past predictions with observations, and co-design the visualisation of climate information. In addition, discussions about the winery decision-making processes were useful to start defining decision trees for the economic value assessment to be carried out later on in the project.

More detail about the first meeting:

BSC visited Codorniu's premises in Raimat, Lleida (Spain) on the 16th of March 2023 for a joint meeting that lasted around 3 hours. The meeting covered the following points:

¹ <https://www.visca.eu/>

1. Brief presentation of the project
2. Introduction of the Codorniu team, background and familiarity with climate information
3. Understand the Super User general attitude towards probabilistic information and expectations regarding ASPECT results
4. Climate prediction specific questions, including:
 - Needs and motivations regarding adaptation to climate change in the medium and long term
 - Super User decisions that depend on future climate
 - Decisions and adaptation measures likely to have the greatest impact
 - The added value of seamless climate information vs current climate information

Some supporting slides were used to introduce the project to the Codorniu staff participating in the meeting. Slides presented some climate related topics that are important to clarify to guide the discussion. Concepts covered included:

- Time horizons of climate predictions (including seasonal predictions, decadal predictions, and climate change projections). Weather features (e.g. extreme events)
- Concept of skill or quality of the predictions
- Layers of information
 - Climate-related variables (e.g. surface temperature, precipitation)
 - Climate-related indicators (e.g. extreme heat, hydrological drought)
 - Risk-informed hazard indicators considering the user vulnerability and adaptation tipping points
- Geographical scale & downscaling: spatial resolution
- Concept of seamless climate information and opportunities regarding current (individual) climate information

Introduction of the Codorniu team

Attendees:

- *Joan Esteve*: Director. Agronomist. He oversees the decisions about the vineyards and the production
- *Jordi Civit*: Agronomist. Dealing with vineyard management. Planning of workload and treatments. They apply preventive treatments, not reactive treatments
- *Xavi Bordes*: Agronomist. Dealing with irrigation management

Joan mentioned that the focus is not to maximise the quantity of grapes (as it is usually done in other agricultural sectors), but to reach the appropriate quality and see which variety they can use for that (quality divided in A, B and C). To control the quality of the wine they apply precision viticulture which is intended to monitor the level of stress affecting the plants. To exploit the vineyard in the best possible way, it is necessary to consider all the terrain characteristics, the incident solar radiation and also the soil depth. This monitoring is done twice a year with an aeroplane which allows for optimising the performance of the vineyard and the wine production. However, they also mentioned there are trends in production at the hemispheric level that can be related to the temperature and solar radiation and its influence on flowering.

Codorniu produces its own grapes and normally does not purchase grapes or wine from third parties. However, they usually distribute the resources between their vineyards in Raimat and

Penedes. For example, in 2022, the production in Penedes was very low due to the drought, and they supplied this lack of production with grapes from Raimat. The most abundant variety they have is Chardonnay.

Spring is the most important season for the wine industry, as March is when they plan what they are going to sell in 3-4 years' time. This planning relies on a combination of strategy and how the market could evolve. Nowadays, the market dictates that the consumption of red wine is going down while it grows the consumption of white wines and cava.

Jordi mentioned that the quantity of grapes that they aim to produce in a particular campaign, involves a particular number of interventions. A big part of their production is ecological (the aim is to be fully ecologic).

Xavier explained that they deal with 800 irrigation valves, for us to get an idea of the complexity that this entails. They expect rain during winter and autumn, but not the rest of the year, but Codorniu does not depend on rain for the irrigation since they irrigate with water from the Canal d'Aragó I Catalunya, which is available as long as there is snow in the Pyrenees.

3.4 Super User attitude towards probabilistic information and expectations

Codorniu has been previously involved in other climate-related projects, where they have explored the use of climate predictions for decision making (e.g. the [VISCA project](#)² – Vineyards integrated smart climate application; see example in Figure 6). In VISCA, where Codorniu collaborated with BSC, seasonal predictions of environmental climate variables such as temperature and precipitation were explored to support operational decisions such as pruning, crop forcing, soil management (cover crops or tillage) and irrigation.

Figure 6. Example of the seasonal predictions of precipitation based on tercile probabilities provided within the VISCA project. These are the seasonal predictions initialised on the 1st of May 2019 for

² <https://www.visca.eu/>

each month from May to October and the probability of the rainfall conditions being below-normal (blue), normal (yellow/orange) and above-normal (red).

Hence, this Super User has experience on how to deal with probabilistic climate predictions and their potential to inform specific decision-making processes. However, their knowledge of decadal climate predictions and climate projections is still limited. In this framework, their expectations from the ASPECT project are related to acquiring better climate knowledge at different time scales. They expect seasonal predictions to be a valuable tool for them to improve growth cycle management, decadal predictions to identify where they should put their focus in terms of investments or research and climate projections to take business strategic decisions.

3.5 Super User decisions on different time scales

From the discussions, the main climate related impacts on grapes/wine were:

- **Frost and hail:** frost has been especially important in the last 3 years (2020-2021-2022), but in the previous 15 years it was not an issue. The critical season for frost is spring, as just one night of frost (i.e., temperature below 0°C) can damage the whole production as this might lead to slower growth of the plants. Regarding the probability of frost, the indicator of minimum temperature from 20th March to 20th April could be useful since the plant has already burst. If the probability of having frost increases in the future (e.g., in the next decade), the company will invest in a de-icing system. What can be done with a seasonal prediction of frost? At the strategic level, they can prune to delay bud break. Also apply water to have an igloo effect and avoid that temperature going below zero. On a seasonal scale, it is also relevant to have information about frost for bud break and post-frost prediction models, because as the season progresses, frosts have a greater impact. On a decadal scale, the information on the spring frosts is relevant to make an investment in frost prevention systems.
- **Mildew** (but less affectation than frost & hail)
- **Temperature/Solar radiation:** when the plant is developed (and it has leaves), solar radiation can affect the quality of the wine. For example, in the case of red wine, the maturation is slower than for other varieties, and the seasonal evolution of the temperature can play an important role. They are usually expecting a decrease in the temperatures at night in August for the Raimat vineyards, and if this is not happening, the harvesting is affected.
- **Heatwaves:** when a heatwave is predicted to come, they need to irrigate at least one week in advance. They 'play' with stressing the plant, but they cannot afford to arrive at a hot period with stress. In this context, a drought index (SPEI), which accounts for precipitation and temperature, could provide valuable information for them.
- **Drought/Rain:** in spring 2023 they experienced a meteorological drought (i.e., no rain), but they had some water in the reservoirs. However, if there is no rain in the upcoming weeks/month water resources would be scarce (i.e., hydrological drought) and they would have water restrictions. Particularly, the CHE (management authority

of the Ebro River basin) has announced a 20% water restriction on the vineyard but also for other agricultural activities in the area if there is no rain after the spring drought.

Specific decisions related to cross-time-scales climate impacts

[Frost]

- Invest in frost prevention systems (decadal)
- Apply management actions to delay bud-break and avoid major damages (e.g., pruning) (seasonal)

[Heatwaves]

- Irrigation to protect the plant (seasonal)

[Drought]

- Buy more grapes to other producers (seasonal, annual). Will also depend on the length of the drought, if it affects one season/year or several years (if the temperature is high and there is a lack of rain, the production is lower and then they might have to buy the grapes)

3.6 Informing co-design of the agriculture case study

The case study defined for the wine sector will include two different decisions that viticulturists need to make at different time scales: 1) Spring frost protection and 2) Water management, both relevant from the seasonal to decadal time scales. A description of the technical specifications required for each of the decisions are included in Tables 1 and 2.

For the spring frost protection, short-to-medium-term information can inform management actions to delay bud-break and avoid major damages (e.g. pruning), while longer-term information can support decisions on whether to invest in frost prevention systems. To this end, BSC is co-producing seasonal predictions of essential climate variables and indicators of extreme conditions of interest for Codorniu, including spring frost days. UOXF is developing a temporal merging methodology to coproduce a seamless climate information product in the seasonal to multi-annual to decadal timescales on spring frost risk over Catalonia. Temporally-merged forecasts of frost days are found to have more consistent skill in the seasonal to multi-annual time-range by combining the ECMWF 7-month, 13-month and 24 months forecast output. This aims to provide added-value information suitable for meeting Codorniu's climate information needs.

For water management, short-medium-term information can anticipate water restrictions so that the users might assume a lower production and decide to buy grapes to other producers, while longer-term information on drought conditions may also impact the choice of other crops to be planted in the following years, for example, those with lower water demand. Multi-annual climate information for the next few years has been generated by BSC for mean temperature and precipitation, indicators of changes in frequency and intensity of extreme minimum and maximum temperature and precipitation, and indicators of drought conditions produced with decadal forecast systems contributing to the Coupled Model Intercomparison

Project Phase 6³/the Decadal Climate Prediction Project⁴, as well as the multi-model ensemble and predictions based on climatology and persistence. In addition, an indicator of compound hot-dry extremes is also being included in the case study by BSC. The quality of such predictions is also available so that the user is informed on the trustworthiness of the climate information.

Table 1. Specifications and levels of climate information required for supporting the spring frost protection decision.

Decision-Making: Spring frost protection			
<p>The critical season for frost is spring, as just one night of frost (i.e., temperature below 0°C) can damage the whole production. This might lead to the death of the shoot since the new shoots that will appear often carry much less fruit than the original ones.</p> <p>In the short-medium term, they can apply management actions to delay bud-break and avoid major damages (e.g., pruning). In the long term, they may invest in frost prevention systems. Another action would consist in choosing varieties with delayed bud-break and/or selecting the most appropriate soil management strategy (e.g. tillage, no intervention etc).</p>			
Specifications			
Location/Region:	Raimat and Penedés (Catalonia, Spain)	Target Period:	20th March - 1st May
Forecast type:	Seasonal predictions Decadal predictions	Spatial Resolution:	farm level (one value for the whole domain)
Lead time (how much in advance should the prediction be available):	November/December	Frequency (how often the info should be updated):	monthly updates
Levels of climate information			
Climate-related variables:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Daily minimum temperature - Dewpoint (accounting for temperature and humidity) - Humidity at night -- below normal - Wind speed at night--below normal 	Climate-related indicators:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Percentage of days in a season with temperatures below 0°C - Percentage of days in a season with the minimum temperature below 10th percentile - Cold spell duration index

³ <https://pcmdi.llnl.gov/CMIP6/>

⁴ wcrp-climate.org/modelling-wgcm-mip-catalogue/cmip6-endorsed-mips-article/1065-modelling-cmip6-dcpp

Risk-informed hazard indicators		Risk indices:	
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Table 2. Specifications and levels of climate information required for supporting the water management decision.

Decision-Making: Water management			
<p>Codorniu counts with an irrigation system in the vineyards. In the case of droughts, they will need to irrigate if there is water available in the reservoirs. If there are water restrictions, they might have to assume a lower production and decide to buy more grapes to other producers. This will depend on the length of the drought, i.e., whether it affects one season/year or several years. It is also important to account for the availability of water in the basin, considering upstream reservoirs and snow in the Pyrenees.</p>			
Specifications			
Location/Region:	Raimat and Penedés (Catalonia, Spain) Pyrenees	Target Period:	April-September Winter Full year
Forecast type:	Seasonal predictions Decadal predictions	Spatial Resolution:	Farm level Sub-basin level (Noguera Ribagorçana and Ésera)
Lead time (how much in advance should the prediction be available):	6 months one year or more (to select the type of crops)	Frequency (how often the info should be updated):	Monthly
Levels of climate information			
Climate-related variables:	-Precipitation -Mean temperature -Maximum temperature -Relative humidity Jul-Aug (<40%) -Wind speed	Climate-related indicators:	- Evapotranspiration -Drought indices (e.g., SPEI) -Heat wave indices (e.g., Heat wave magnitude index, >36°C/38°C during various continuous days)
Risk-informed hazard indicators		Risk indices:	

4 Finance (Pensions sector)

4.1 Summary of Super User Decision Making Context

User engagement has revealed that the sector is currently at a very early stage in its understanding of climate change risks to existing and future investment decisions. Consequently, the relationships between ASPECT via the Met Office with the sector are being largely developed from scratch and ASPECT is using mediators to help navigate and engage with the pensions sector to understand their requirements. The pension sector generally has a **low appreciation of the physical risk** associated with climate change in their investments, and so there is an opportunity for ASPECT to contribute to **systemic change** of the sector toward sustainability and steering economic activities toward **socially beneficial outcomes**.

The investments of pension funds are typically **diverse** in terms of sector (built environment, agriculture, transport, infrastructure, manufacturing etc) and geographically diverse – pension funds invest globally. There is also a need to assess and manage risks within the current portfolios and assess the inherent risks (climate and otherwise) of investments they hold currently as well as new investments pension funds are asked to make now and in the future. By better assessing and managing these risks, pension funds will be better able to achieve sustained long-term income from such investments to ensure they can meet their legal obligation to pay pensions on time, in full, as they fall due. From the perspective of climate variability and change, this means that the **time scales of interest span the whole range considered by ASPECT and beyond** as pension liabilities extend far into the future, with promises being made today having a lifespan of well over 50 years. Due to the diverse nature of this sector, this case study is ideal for considering potential **upscaling** throughout the climate service development.

Our understanding of the decision making context of pension funds has identified that to **drive change** in the sector, we should design a case study to illustrate the potential **underestimation of physical and financial** risk carried by pension funds who are not incorporating future climate information into their investment decision making. This aims to empower funds globally to identify which investments are less exposed to climate risks or more resilient to the impacts of climate change. This will create change in the market by raising climate risk awareness with these investors, who have the power to influence asset managers across a wide range of investment types.

4.2 Wider context of European financial investment

Financial markets are widely recognized as key catalysts for change due to their wide, far-reaching impacts and influence on broader socio-economic factors. Decisions made within the financial system, for example, where capital is channelled into the real economy via investment, flow through financial markets, to the economy and more broadly into

society. The ‘feedback effect’ underpins the process of financial asset prices providing ‘signals’ to decision makers in the wider economy ([Goldstein, 2023](#)).

One of the key financial institutions in this system are pension funds, which hold at least USD 53 trillion and are one of the biggest global asset owners globally ([Thinking Ahead Institute, 2021](#)). The [European Fund and Asset Management Association \(2021\)](#) found 85% of asset management in Europe is concentrated in the key financial centres of the United Kingdom, France, Germany, Switzerland, the Netherlands and Italy, with European asset managers managing total assets of over EUR 30 trillion.

Pension funds invest across several different spatial and temporal scales for their beneficiaries to meet their legal obligations (fiduciary duty) to pay pensions in full, on time, as they fall due. As one of the largest asset owners, pension funds have the potential to significantly alter financial markets globally. Through channelling funds to ‘green’ investments, allocating their capital to different sectors, such as green infrastructure projects, they have a significant impact on the economic landscape. For example, pension funds can support the growth and innovation of emerging markets, small and medium enterprises, and green technologies by providing them with long-term patient capital.

Some examples of green financing include the European Commission Project Bonds which were created to finance transport, energy and information and communication technologies infrastructure ([European Fund and Asset Management Association, 2021](#)). NextGenerationEU bonds now also exist to help with the green transition and to build European resilience ([European Commission, 2022](#)), while the UK Government has been issuing [Green Gilts](#)⁵. Another example is healthcare provision for the changing demographics of our society, with a fivefold investment in healthcare by European equity investment funds between 2010 and 2020 ([European Fund and Asset Management Association, 2021](#)).

The financing of low carbon technologies that will help society transition to a more sustainable economy is another way that asset owners can invest for the benefit of pension fund members and wider society, while reducing climate risk in their portfolios. Environmental, social and governance (‘ESG’) criteria are increasingly incorporated into investment decision making and risk management processes. However, to achieve current societal climate goals of limiting global temperature rise to well below 2°C, both climate adaptation and mitigation financing need to increase by 3-6 times their current levels over the next decade ([Intergovernmental Panel for Climate Change, 2023](#)).

In Figure 7, the Network for Greening the Financial System (2024) highlights how the financing of adaptation measures to reduce vulnerability and physical risk exposure can have a range of economic and financial impacts. The Network for Greening the Financial System (2024) emphasises that ‘preventative investment in risk reduction is the most cost-effective approach to addressing disaster costs as these costs can then be avoided for multiple occurrences of disaster events’.

⁵ <https://www.dmo.gov.uk/responsibilities/green-gilts/>

Figure 7: Ways that financing of adaptation measures reduce vulnerability and physical risk exposure (from [Network for Greening the Financial System, 2024](#))

4.3 Challenges across the pension sector

Pension funds are increasingly motivated to understand the implications of climate change for their activities due to, but not exclusively by, the implementation of additional climate related **regulation** such as the [Climate-related Financial Disclosure Regulations](#)⁶ in the UK, and (until October 2023) the [Task Force for Climate-Related Financial Disclosures](#)⁷, now replaced by the International Sustainability Standards Board (ISSB) International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS S1 General Requirements for Disclosure of Sustainability-related Financial Information and IFRS S2 Climate-related Disclosures⁸). However, although climate related disclosures are increasing substantially year-on-year, the [Task Force for Climate-Related Financial Disclosures \(2022\)](#) noted concern that few companies are disclosing decision-useful climate related financial information, hindering the assessment and pricing of climate related risks. Table 1 outlines the information that the [Task Force for Climate-Related Financial Disclosures \(2022\)](#) recommends be included in financial disclosure reporting, and highlights the type of information that a financial sector asset owner might wish to understand about the assets in their portfolio. The IFRS Foundation reported in 2024 that "based on a sample of 3,814 public companies, in fiscal year 2023 82% of companies disclosed information in line with at least one of the 11 TCFD recommended disclosures and 44% of companies with at least five of the recommended disclosures. Approximately 2–3% of companies reported in line with all 11 TCFD recommended disclosures" ([IFRS Foundation, 2024](#)).

Managers and trustees of pension funds may be additionally motivated by the growth of the **Net Zero by 2050** agenda in recent years and may align their assets to fulfil their core

⁶www.gov.uk/government/publications/climate-related-financial-disclosures-for-companies-and-limited-liability-partnerships-llps

⁷www.fsb-tcfd.org/

⁸ <https://www.ifrs.org/content/dam/ifrs/supporting-implementation/ifrs-s2/ifrs-s2-comparison-tcfd.pdf>

stakeholder needs and demands as well as managing the implied risks of a societal transition to net-Zero. In the UK, The Pensions Regulator ('TPR') analysed reports from pensions schemes (with over £1 billion in assets under management) that are required to publish climate reports since 2022, finding that 60% of the sampled reports included a net zero goal of some kind for 2050 or before, although this is not a requirement for trustees ([TPR, 2024](#)).

However, TPR also recommends that these reports could be improved by “considering a qualitative analysis based on clear narratives while quantitative analysis is still developing in the market” and “providing commentary on the challenges and limitations”, implying that **quantitative risk analysis is rare** ([TPR, 2024](#)). TPR has also stated during 2024 that “while most trustees meet their environmental social governance (ESG) duties, many achieve only **minimum compliance**” ([TPR, 2024](#)).

Current pension **liabilities extend beyond 2100**, as pension liabilities can exceed the human lifespan when they pass to descendants (e.g., [Irene Triplett](#) received an American Civil War (1861-5) pension until her death in 2020), providing further impetus for long term thinking (Phillips, 2020). Over these timescales, we are already locked into significant climate impacts, such as sea level rise, which the UK Climate Projections and International Panel of Climate Change projections show may increase by over 1 metre around the UK by 2100 and more than 2 metres by 2300 ([Weeks et al. 2023](#)). Almost 50 million people (and related infrastructure) in Europe live below 10 metre elevation ([McEvoy et al. 2021](#)) and so these are very real risks both for society and for the investments that pension funds currently hold and will make in the future.

Currently, there is a **lack of scientifically robust and decision-useful tools** for helping the financial sector to make decisions around climate change and adaptation. The financial sector does not contain much deep expertise within its industry to provide effective risk management of climate risks, and while many consultancies do provide products, these are often 'black-box' methodologies that do not provide confidence around scientific robustness nor sufficient evaluation of uncertainties.

Table 3. TCFD Recommendations and Supporting Recommended Disclosures (from Task Force for Climate-Related Financial Disclosures (2022 status report)).

Governance	Strategy	Risk Management	Metrics and Targets
<p>Disclose the company's governance around climate-related risks and opportunities.</p>	<p>Disclose the actual and potential impacts of climate-related risks and opportunities on the company's businesses, strategy, and financial planning where such information is material.</p>	<p>Disclose how the company identifies, assesses, and manages climate-related risks.</p>	<p>Disclose the metrics and targets used to assess and manage relevant climate-related risks and opportunities where such information is material.</p>
<p>a) Describe the board's oversight of climate-related risks and opportunities.</p>	<p>a) Describe the climate-related risks and opportunities the company has identified over the short, medium, and long term.</p>	<p>a) Describe the company's processes for identifying and assessing climate-related risks.</p>	<p>a) Disclose the metrics used by the company to assess climate-related risks and opportunities in line with its strategy and risk management process.</p>
<p>b) Describe management's role in assessing and managing climate-related risks and opportunities.</p>	<p>b) Describe the impact of climate-related risks and opportunities on the company's businesses, strategy, and financial planning.</p>	<p>b) Describe the company's processes for managing climate-related risks.</p>	<p>b) Disclose Scope 1, Scope 2, and, if appropriate, Scope 3 greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, and the related risks.</p>
	<p>c) Describe the resilience of the company's strategy, taking into consideration different climate-related scenarios, including a 2°C or lower scenario.</p>	<p>c) Describe how processes for identifying, assessing, and managing climate-related risks are integrated into the company's overall risk management.</p>	<p>c) Describe the targets used by the company to manage climate-related risks and opportunities and performance against targets.</p>

4.4 The needs of the pensions sector

Asset owners need to **balance climate risk with other risks that pension funds are exposed to in their wider risk assessment**, with portfolios of assets being exposed to a wide array of different risks, many of which will also be influenced indirectly by climate change as climate change acts a ‘threat multiplier’ across society.

Asset owners need better understanding of the climate risk **already in their portfolios**, as well as any climate risks in **potential investments** they are being asked to make. They can use this information to help understand how risks evolve over time, and to improve their risk management, as well as thinking about climate resilience in the new investments that the pension fund does make.

Currently, most asset owners **do not understand the physical risks** of climate change well enough to incorporate them into their investment decision-making. Building the capability of asset owners to align an understanding of physical climate risk to assets with the needs of the pensions sector will benefit them as they will be better able to understand their **potential liabilities**, and **challenge advice from asset managers** who may also not be aware of or have a good understanding of how climate change may affect pension liabilities.

Providing potential asset owners with an understanding of physical climate risk can help them identify potential **physical climate risk to a new or on-going investment** and may empower the investor to **negotiate for additional criteria to be implemented** (e.g., social housing design could be made more livable in future increased temperatures and heatwaves in summer, or more resilient to surface water flooding from intense rainfall in the winter). Asset owners may also be motivated to participate in **cooperative efforts** across a catchment area to implement adaptation measures to protect multiple assets and reduce risk across specific geographic areas (e.g. [sustainable drainage systems](#)⁹).

The pensions sector is particularly concerned about **protracted risk** from chronic (long-term) impacts and prolonged periods of climate variability which may impact the portfolio of the fund, **reducing the returns** through asset stranding, transition risks, or from returns from specific investments being lower than expected, all of which risks the ability of the fund to meet their **obligations** to make regular pension payments both today and in the future.

4.5 What climate information is the pensions sector interested in?

Due to the diverse portfolios involved in the pensions sector, like those that [ClearGlass Analytics](#)¹⁰ are assessing and evaluating, asset owners need to have a **broad awareness of climate risks** across different sectors of society. Climate can potentially impact every investment that a pension fund makes.

⁹ <https://thefloodhub.co.uk/sustainable-drainage-systems-suds-toolkit/>

¹⁰ <https://www.clearglass.com/>

Figure 8: From [NGFS Climate Scenarios for central banks and supervisors, Network for Greening the Financial System \(June 2021\)](#)

Figure 8 illustrates the range of **pathways** by which climate risks can affect the economy and financial system, illustrated as transmission channels. They are categorised as micro (impacting businesses and households) or macro (impacts on the broader economy) ([NGFS, 2021](#)).

Here the focus is on physical climate risk. Firstly, **chronic impacts** stem from longer term changes to climate, particularly from increased temperatures, sea level rise and changes to precipitation patterns, and over time, may affect labour, capital, land, and other natural capital. Chronic risks will require a significant level of investment and adaptation from companies, households and governments ([NGFS, 2021](#)).

Secondly, **acute impacts from extreme weather** events include direct damage to assets and losses due to disruption, and with increased frequency and severity these may lead to persistent longer term impacts on the economy. Such acute events may increase underwriting risks for insurers, which may have implications for insurance coverage in some regions, as well as affecting the value of assets ([NGFS, 2021](#)).

European society is already being impacted by extreme weather, with weather and climate related extremes resulting in **economic losses of EUR 783 billion in EU** member states during 1980-2023, of which 22% occurred between 2021 and 2023 ([European Environment Agency, 2024](#), and Figure 9).

Flooding has resulted in 44% of these losses over 1980-2021. Heatwaves were responsible for 19% of losses, with droughts, forest fires and cold waves also resulting in substantial losses. Extreme events are key to financial losses: “5% of climate-related events with the biggest losses are responsible for 61% of losses, and 1% of the events cause 28% of losses” ([European Environment Agency, 2024](#)). Key events include the German and Belgian flooding in 2021 (costing nearly EUR 50 billion), central European flooding in 2002 (over EUR 22

billion) and the extensive drought and heatwave in 2003 (EUR 16 billion) ([European Environment Agency, 2024](#)). Reuters reported that the devastating floods in eastern Spain in early November 2024 may result in over EUR 10 billion of damages to local businesses, with banks loan exposure to the area worth around EUR 20 billion ([Aguado, 2024](#)).

Extreme events are going to become more frequent and severe globally over the coming decades, with physical climate risks increasingly interacting with non-climatic risk creating **compounding** and **cascading risk** across different sectors ([Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2023](#)). There is an imperative for the finance and pensions sectors to consider climate risk in a meaningful way as well as integrating it systemically through their risk assessment processes.

Figure 9. Annual economic damage caused by weather- and climate-related extreme events in the EU Member States ([European Environment Agency, 2024](#)).

4.6 Engagement with Super User during 2023 and 2024

The relationships between ASPECT via the Met Office with the pensions sector are being largely developed from scratch and ASPECT is using two **mediators** to help navigate and engage with the pensions sector to understand their requirements. These are [Professor Iain Clacher](#)¹¹, who is a pensions expert at the University of Leeds and a member of the [Centre for Greening Financial Investments](#)¹² (a UK based research initiative created to accelerate the adoption and use of climate and environmental data and analytics by financial institutions internationally), and the company [ClearGlass Analytics](#)¹³.

ClearGlass Analytics is an independent data company and technology platform that was created to help asset owners (i.e., pension funds) assess value for money delivered by their asset managers. ClearGlass is a platform which collects costs and charges data from asset managers on behalf of asset owners or their advisors to increase transparency across the industry, so pension funds can discover, analyse, and compare their costs. They have assets of around £1.3 trillion on their platform and ClearGlass are therefore able to provide an important role increasing the exposure of project outputs across the sector and facilitating links to specific pensions funds.

There has been additional direct engagement with the **pensions fund managers** for Tesco (the UK's largest supermarket), as well as several meetings with the **The Pensions Regulator** in the UK to better understand the needs of the pensions sector and whether the proposed design of the case study would be useful for the sector as a tool to leverage change by stimulating a wider consideration of physical climate risk across the sector. In addition, there has been engagement with the financial sector more broadly, as many concerns of the insurance industry are very applicable to the pensions sector so there are many synergies as to how climate services could benefit both industries. The insurance sector is typically more active and engaged with the climate services community at the present time, and several ASPECT members attended an event '[Collaborating for Impact: Bridging the Gap Between Climate Science and Insurance Industry Practice](#)'¹⁴ in Leeds, UK, which 95 people attended, 45 from the insurance industry. One of the work package leads has also attended an event of the Oasis Loss Modelling Framework in London.

The ASPECT project team are additionally informed by other projects working with different areas of the financial sector. For example, the Met Office developed a [Copernicus Climate Change Service \(C3S\) Sectoral Applications of Decadal Predictions project](#)¹⁵ focusing on the insurance sector, working with the Willis Research network. The project identified a need for seasonal to decadal information to be useful and usable to the stakeholder (typically probabilistic outputs from decadal prediction systems are not easy for insurers to use directly). Time is required to build relationships and trust with stakeholders to enable the successful co-production of usable climate information. In addition, the timeliness of

¹¹ <https://business.leeds.ac.uk/departments-accounting-finance/staff/55/professor-iain-clacher>

¹² <https://www.cgfi.ac.uk/>

¹³ <https://www.clearglass.com/>

¹⁴ <https://www.cgfi.ac.uk/2024/06/collaborating-for-impact-insurance/>

¹⁵ <https://climate.copernicus.eu/decadal-predictions-insurance>

information is very important for the insurance sector, as users require seasonal/interannual forecasts to be available at the right time of year for them to use, e.g., to give them the opportunity to influence their policy pricing.

4.7 Informing co-design of the pension sector case study

The pensions sector case study has been designed as a climate service to leverage change across the financial sector, specifically to highlight the physical risk that pension funds may be carrying within their existing portfolios and present an example of this in a way that is persuasive to key actors in decision making for pension funds. Typically, people working in the financial sector tend to have a low appreciation of physical risk associated with climate change, with far more importance given to other factors in their investment decision making process. The people across the industry that we have engaged with typically have a limited understanding of climate risk making discussion of scientific specifics very difficult, and information sharing is very difficult due to commercial sensitivities. This means that a key objective of the case study is to design a service which **clearly conveys key messages around potential losses from physical climate risk** to people with very little understanding of climate information, with **transparent methodology** available and **robust scientific principles** underpinning its creation.

Pension funds as global investors have many assets that span large geographic areas. As financial losses are a major driver in decision making in the pensions sector, the initial case study has been designed to focus on risk associated from **damage to assets** across Europe, from **heavy precipitation** which is typically associated with flooding on a broad scale. The hazard information on heavy precipitation (rainfall extremes) will be initially extracted from current climate and future climate period of future projections from state-of-the-art ensembles of a regional climate model, as well as decadal predictions, as the case study will span consideration of decadal and future climate timescales. Using climate model hazard rainfall event frequency to infer flood frequency is a different approach to the very localised approach of hydrological flood modelling, which is best practice for a local flood risk assessment for a particular asset, but it is the only feasible way identified to create a pan-Europe prototype service, and to enable broad scale **assessment of risk** and **conversion to potential losses** which is required by the sector. Table 4 outlines some of the possible specifications for data required for this climate service prototype.

By providing illustrative examples of potential climate related losses in synthetic portfolios, it is envisaged that the prototype climate service may influence **decision making** in the following ways:

- Increase the level of **understanding** across pensions funds actors of the financial impact that physical climate risk may have on pensions portfolios.
- Stimulate additional effort to **quantitatively assess climate risk** to existing assets in pension portfolios.
- Increase the consideration of climate risk associated with **tomorrow's investments**, and empower investors to **champion adaptation** to reduce risk, during building construction or later development. This could include collective efforts to protect pools

of assets across at-risk areas.

- Demonstrate **regional variations** in risk, which offers options to **diversify risk** through geographic consideration of assets, particularly to offset other losses in the near term, and identify areas for investment which may be associated with less climate risk. Note that the intention is certainly not to encourage any wide-scale regional dis-investment, but rather encourage climate adaptation efforts to address climate risk.

Table 4. Specifications and levels of climate information required for supporting decision-making across the pensions sector, and particularly for the case study.

Decision-Making: Understanding how physical climate risk from inland flooding might influence pension portfolios in Europe and how this may change over the next 30 years			
<p>As financial losses are a major driver in decision making in the pensions sector, the initial case study has been designed to focus on risk associated from damage to assets across Europe, from heavy precipitation which is typically associated with flooding on a broad scale.</p>			
Specifications			
Location/Region:	<p>Europe</p> <p>Note that some assets may be outside Europe or be indirectly affected by impacts outside Europe, but the primary focus for the case study will be the European domain.</p>	Target Period:	<p>Decadal to climate timescales.</p> <p>Although there is an interest in seasonal to interannual time scale information, demonstrating potential changes to climate and associated financial risk on decadal timescales is the priority for this case study.</p>
		Spatial Resolution:	<p>The financial sector can potentially benefit from the highest spatial resolution that science can deliver for variables, particularly where this is known to provide improvement over lower resolution (e.g., heavy rainfall).</p> <p>Hazard information at the resolution of individual assets is desired but is not possible at current climate</p>

			model resolution. The highest resolution climate projection models spanning Europe have a horizontal resolution of ~12 km, with decadal prediction model horizontal resolution ~60 km.
Lead time (how much in advance should the prediction be available):	The financial sector can potentially benefit from the longest lead time that science can meaningfully deliver, as investment decisions span a range of time scales.	Frequency (how often should information be updated):	The financial sector can potentially benefit from the highest frequency updates to predictions that science can meaningfully deliver. An ideal frequency should capture changes to the signal in a robust way and be cognisant of the multiple timescales that an asset might be exposed to impactful weather and climate events on.
Levels of climate information			
Climate related variables:	For the case study, we are focusing on using rainfall data . A wide range of climate related variables that can be delivered with confidence will be needed for a wider assessment of physical climate risk, and this might include maximum, minimum and mean temperature, rainfall and other contributing variables relating to wildfire, health and asset damage such as wind and humidity.	Climate related indicators: In addition to physical risk indicators European Central Bank Climate change related indicators ¹⁶ also include sustainable finance and carbon emissions, which will be	A wide range of climate related indicators that can be delivered with confidence and with uncertainty estimates. The European Central Bank suggests 'indicators used to quantify physical risks should cover as many acute natural hazards as possible'. The pensions sector is particularly concerned about protracted risk from chronic (long-term) impacts and prolonged periods of climate variability which may impact the portfolio, reducing profitability and risking the ability of the fund to meet

¹⁶www.ecb.europa.eu/stats/all-key-statistics/horizontal-indicators/sustainability-indicators/html/index.en.html

		out of our scope.	their obligation to make regular pension payments.
Risk informed hazard indicators	Physical risk indicators currently used by the European Central Bank ¹⁷ : coastal and river flooding, wind storms, water stress, wildfire, landslides and subsistence.	Risk indices:	<p>The case study will develop risk indices dependent on the specifics of case study portfolio/s and the provision of suitable exposure and vulnerability information. A primary risk metric is potential financial losses over a particular time period.</p> <p>Hazard specific risk scores can indicate the percentage of a portfolio associated with no/low/medium/high risk (European Central Bank, 2023¹⁸).</p>

¹⁷www.ecb.europa.eu/pub/pdf/other/ecb.climate_change_indicators202301~47c4bbbc92.en.pdf

¹⁸www.ecb.europa.eu/stats/all-key-statistics/horizontal-indicators/sustainability-indicators/data/shared/files/2023-02-06_Climate_change_indicators_Stakeholder_seminar.pdf

5 Governance (EU Mission on Climate Adaptation)

5.1 Summary of Super User Decision Making Context

The [EU Climate Law](#) (EU Regulation 2021/1119) mandates that Member States adopt and implement a national adaptation strategy and plan, guided by the EU adaptation strategy. The national adaptation strategies are to be rooted in comprehensive climate risk assessments, regularly updated and focused on the most vulnerable sectors. In line with the EU Climate Law's mandate, the international standard “Adaptation to climate change — Guidelines on vulnerability, impacts and risk assessment” (ISO 14091:2021)¹⁹ provides a framework to assess climate risks, evaluate vulnerabilities, and plan effective adaptation solutions. Complementary to this, the [Union Civil Protection Mechanism](#) (UCPM, Decision 1313/2013/EU) mandates that Member States carry out disaster risk assessments at the national or suitable sub-national level and submit reports every three years on key risks. These reports should address risks with cross-border implications, disasters with potential multi-country transboundary effects, and, where relevant, low-probability but high-impact risks. A range of other sectoral EU legislation contains similar requirements for conducting and communicating sectoral risk assessments, such as the EU [Floods Directive](#) (Directive 2007/60/EC) and the EU Directive on the [Resilience of Critical Entities](#) (Directive 2022/2557/EU).

Climate risk assessments for adaptation strategies should identify key risks, set management priorities, align with various regulatory requirements, and deliver consistent spatial and temporal information through impact, resilience stress and adaptation performance assessments. To meet diverse requirements, risk assessments can be delivered in various forms, including individual indicators or composite indices, projections or forecasts, trend analyses, and social, economic, or environmental analyses related to climate, providing valuable insights for society at large. While risk assessments traditionally focus on hazard, exposure, and vulnerability dimensions, the IPCC Sixth Assessment Report report (AR6, WGII - [Chapter 1](#), Ara Begum, 2022) also highlights risks arising from policy responses, including maladaptation and unintended impacts of climate policies. In summary, a climate risk assessment provides essential insights for national and regional adaptation strategies by analysing the evolving landscape of climate-related hazards and risks and their potential to propagate through interconnected pathways, impacting multiple sectors of society.

5.2 EU Mission on climate change

The EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation 2021-2027, the Horizon Europe (HE), established five research and innovation-oriented Missions, one of which is the EU Mission on adaptation to climate change (hereafter referred to as Mission Adaptation or Mission). The Implementation Plan of the Mission outlines the roadmap and targets for achieving its objectives and vision. The primary objective of the Mission is to enable at least 150 European regions and communities to become climate-resilient by 2030, while also delivering a minimum of 75 large-scale demonstrations of systemic transformations towards climate resilience. These goals align with the overall aim of the Mission to create a more resilient and adapted Europe, better equipped to face the impacts of climate change.

¹⁹ <https://www.iso.org/standard/68508.html>

The Mission Adaptation plays a vital role in implementing the European Union's 2021 Adaptation Strategy by helping regions in gaining a deeper understanding of the climate risks they face presently and in the future. This understanding is essential in developing effective pathways towards preparing for and coping with the changing climate. The Mission also supports the deployment of innovative solutions on the ground to enhance the resilience of communities to the adverse impacts of climate change. By providing resources and support, regions are empowered to test and evaluate the feasibility and effectiveness of these solutions in real-world scenarios.

The Mission aims to support a diverse range of regions and communities in their journey towards climate risk adaptation, irrespective of their present progress level. To this end, regional and local authorities and action groups sharing the Mission's objectives have expressed their interest in joining by signing the Mission Charter. As of March 2023, 284 regions and local authorities from 25 EU Member States, and 17 regions and local authorities from Associated Countries to Horizon Europe have signed the Mission Charter. Mission's Implementation Platform (MIP) was established in 2023 to assist in implementing the Mission, coordinate the activities involved, provide technical support to regions and local authorities, monitor and report on progress, and encourage wider participation in the Mission. Furthermore, the Mission's portal was launched in April 2023, providing pertinent knowledge, data, and resources to European regional and local authorities, empowering them to prepare and plan for climate resilience.

The Mission has laid out an ambitious framework for local and regional transformative adaptation, aimed at preparing Europe to deal with climate disruptions, accelerating the transformation towards a climate-resilient future, and building deep resilience by scaling up actionable solutions. The roadmap to transformational change, as laid out by the Mission Adaptation, depends on innovations in local and regional climate risk assessments across key community systems most vulnerable to climate change such as health and social care systems, critical infrastructure and entities, water supply, landscape productivity and ecosystem health. The [CLIMAAX](#)²⁰ project sets out to develop a customised framework and toolbox for climate risk assessment at local and regional scales addressing these systems.

Local and regional communities are exposed to various climate risks and lack the necessary resources and tools to effectively cope with and manage them. Many communities lack the necessary information, data and skills to identify and prioritise climate risks, assess their vulnerability, and develop strategies to manage them. This is due to a range of factors such as limited financial resources, technology, or skilled professionals, weak institutional capacity, and political or social barriers. Climate risk assessments are only useful if they contribute to the development of capacity and capability to effectively cope with and manage risks. Communities face difficulties in implementing effective adaptation measures when they lack sufficient knowledge about the evolving and compound patterns of current and future risks caused by extreme weather and climate-related hazards, as well as their vulnerabilities and underlying risk drivers. CLIMAAX helps local and regional communities to gain a deeper understanding of the climate risks they are exposed to, and empower them to take action. The aim of the project is to assist communities in evaluating their past experience and progress in assessing climate change risks, particularly those affecting the key community systems.

²⁰ <https://www.climaax.eu/>

What defines the local and region risk assessment is not solely or primarily the spatial scale. Regional and local assessments of climate risks are used to identify common goals and priorities for coordinated climate action, which are often expressed through collective adaptation plans and strategies. Local or regional climate risk assessments are not solely defined by the spatial scale they cover. Instead, the primary focus of these assessments is on ensuring the prosperity and resilience of the communities in the region, as well as the safety and integrity of the environment in which they reside. Risk assessments may examine how climate variability and change affect farming and food production in rural areas dominated by agriculture, as an example. A regional climate risk assessment doesn't just stop at evaluating the impact on individual farms, but rather it delves deeper to analyse how changes in farm profitability and viability may have a ripple effect on local employment, fiscal revenues, and social services that rely on these revenues. Only such assessment can assist in collective decision-making on how to adapt production practices, support alternative employment opportunities, and maintain essential community services. In essence, regional climate risk assessments may analyse the adverse effects of climate change on prominent businesses but aim to understand the consequences for the whole community. Similarly framed assessments are a critical element in creating a regional adaptation strategy that evaluates risks and opportunities, sets priorities and vision, and coordinates adaptation processes across various aspects of community living.

5.3 Empowering Mission's communities and regions to be a Super User

The ASPECT consortium actively supports the Mission Adaptation by working with a sample of Mission-enrolled regions and communities. The primary objective is to facilitate the use of state-of-the-art, seamless climate information and promote adoption of reliable and quality assured climate predictions. ASPECT aims at showcasing the value proposition of the seamless climate prediction products by assessing their value in reducing climate-induced damage and losses, enabling more efficient natural resource management, and increasing productivity.

To promote the widespread use of ASPECT's knowledge products, the consortium is committed to closely collaborate with communities and regions enrolled in the Mission adaptation. Selected communities and regions are engaged as Super Users in ASPECT WP4. Furthermore, the project will facilitate the dissemination and exploitation of seamless climate information to other regions participating in the Mission adaptation through the Mission Implementation Platform and other ongoing Mission's projects.

As part of our strategy to engage Mission communities and regions as Super Users, the ASPECT project conducted several activities:

- Firstly, we invited interested parties to the ASPECT Multi-sectoral User Forum (MUF) events, which were held in two sessions on March 24th and April 21st, 2024 (see also Deliverable D5.2), as well as from January 30th to February 1st, 2024. Invitations were distributed via the Mission Implementation Platform (MIP) and through various networks such as Local Governments for Sustainability (ICLEI) and the European Association of Development Agencies (EURADA). The Multi-sectoral User Forum (MUF) events were carefully structured to serve dual purposes. Firstly, they aimed to foster a broader understanding of climate forecasts among the Community of

Interest—a group focused on gaining foundational knowledge and exploring the broader impacts of climate information on decision-making. Secondly, the events facilitated in-depth technical discussions and the sharing of lessons learned within the Community of Practice. This community engages with climate forecasts on a technical level, addressing practical applications, data interpretation challenges, and best practices in the implementation of climate-informed strategies.

- Secondly, a collaboration was established with the Mission’s project CLIMAAX, which developed a tailored framework and toolkit for assessing climate risks at the regional and local levels. This collaboration helps communities to assess their past experiences, identify gaps in capacity and capability, and take action to address climate risks. These regional and local climate risk assessments are crucial for collective decision-making, prioritising goals and visions, and coordinating adaptation processes across various aspects of community living. The CLIMAAX framework and toolbox are initially tested in five pilot areas: Finland and Latvia at the national level, and Catalonia (Spain), Setúbal (Portugal), and Zilina (Slovakia) at the sub-national level. The framework and toolbox is being applied to 50 regions as part of the same project. The regions selected for the CLIMAAX project have the opportunity to improve their local and regional climate risk assessments through the use of cascading funds managed by the project, which serve as a catalyst for transformational change. ASPECT contributes to this effort by collaborating closely with the CLIMAAX and the subsequent beneficiaries of the cascading funds. By doing so, ASPECT helps to expand the outreach of the project and incorporate climate predictions into the climate risk assessment framework and toolbox outlined in the Mission’s Implementation Plan.

5.4 Candidate regions

The **Emilia-Romagna region (RER)** is a leading hub of climate innovation in Italy and Europe. As the home to the EIT Climate-Knowledge Innovation Community, the Copernicus Data Centre, and the National Agency for Meteorology and Climatology, RER fosters cutting-edge research, innovation, and industry. The region has also established the Regional Coordination Platform and the Observatory of Climate Change Impacts to promote coherence and synergies among regional planning instruments, harmonise monitoring and evaluation, and ensure effective climate action. In 2018, RER approved its Climate Change Mitigation and Adaptation Strategy, and in 2020, it partnered with businesses, industries, local governments, schools, universities, civil society organisations, and financial institutions to adopt the multi-stakeholder Partnership Agreement for Climate and Jobs. RER is piloting urban blue and green interventions in 11 cities with national funds, and major cities like Bologna and Parma have developed urban adaptation and mitigation plans, joining the EU Mission: Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities. As a signatory of the Mission Charter, RER is committed to achieving climate resilience and a sustainable future.

The Super User was the Regional Agency for Environmental Protection and Energy of Emilia-Romagna (**ARPAE**), a public research institute that operates in the field of environmental protection and energy. ARPAE was created by the Emilia-Romagna region to provide scientific support for the development and implementation of policies related to environmental protection, sustainable development, and energy. ARPAE's activities include monitoring and assessing the quality of air, water, soil, and biodiversity, promoting renewable energy sources and energy efficiency, and providing technical assistance and advice to

public authorities and private entities. The ARPAE Climate Observatory Service is well acquainted with the cutting-edge climate services based on climate prediction. For example, as part of the [H2020 CLARA](#) project, ARPAE developed a climate service called Water Requirements for Irrigation (WRI)²¹ which uses probabilistic seasonal forecasts to estimate whether irrigation demand determined using Earth Observation can be met with the expected water availability. The Agency also provides specialised climate knowledge products for local and regional climate adaptation and mitigation strategies and plans.

Po River Basin District (PRBD) is the largest river basin in Italy and spans six regions, including three enrolled in the Mission Adaptation: Emilia Romagna, Veneto and Autonomous Province of Trento. The district has a highly developed agricultural sector and significant industrial activity, with major urban centres, including Milan and Bologna involved in the EU Mission Climate-neutral and smart cities. The PRBD Authority manages the district, implementing policies to protect water resources, mitigate flood effects, and promote sustainable development. The authority has collaborated with over 30 regional and national organisations to develop a new climate adaptation strategy supported by the EU LIFE program, called ClimaxPo (Climate adaptation for the Po river basin district). The goal is to provide access to advanced climate knowledge to assist in the development of experimental adaptation measures and policies. Veneto is an active participant in climate innovation and research, boasting various research centres and institutions dedicated to climate change. Veneto is also a member of the EIT Climate-KIC Knowledge and Innovation Community, supporting the development of innovative solutions to climate change. To monitor and assess the effects of climate change in the area, Veneto has established a Regional Observatory on Climate Change. As part of the initiative, Veneto ADAPT aims to develop and test evidence-based policies and tools to increase Europe's resilience to the impacts of climate change, especially hydrogeological risks. The project seeks to enhance regional capacity to respond to climate change challenges by promoting networking within the central Veneto conurbation, covering the Metropolitan City of Venice and the Municipalities of Padova, Vicenza, and Treviso. The [H2020 project MYRIAD-EU](#)²² focusses on Veneto to help develop climate multi-risk assessment.

Several European regions have not yet formalised their application to become a super user. These include Lower Austria (AT), Skåne region (SE) and Krapina-Zagorje and Zagreb counties (HR).

- Lower Austria was the first region in Austria to adopt the "climate action programme" (CAP) in 2004 and establish climate mitigation as a fundamental law in its state constitution in 2007. The 2021 revision of the program prioritised adaptation measures for the regional climate agenda. Lower Austria also participates in the [KLAR!](#) program (Climate Adaptation Model Region)²³, which connects municipalities to enhance climate awareness and knowledge sharing.
- Skåne is the southernmost county in Sweden, playing a leadership role in regional climate change and nature-based adaptation. The [Open Skåne 2030](#)²⁴ strategy targets a climate-neutral and fossil-fuel-free Skåne, with a common Climate and Energy strategy adopted by the City Council of Skåne, Skåne Region, and the

²¹ <https://www.clara-project.eu/services/water-requirements-for-irrigation-wri/>

²² <https://www.myriadproject.eu/>

²³ <https://klar-anpassningsregionen.at/service/english-summary>

²⁴

<https://utveckling.skane.se/publikationer/publikationer/the-open-skane-2030---skanes-regional-development-strategy/>

Association of Municipalities in Skåne. The major cities of the regions - Malmö, Lund, and Helsingborg - are part of the EU Mission Cities.

- Krapina-Zagorje and Zagreb counties in Northern Croatia prioritise climate services in their policies and strategies. Krapina-Zagorje is part of the Mission Adaptation, while Zagreb is one of the 100 climate-neutral and smart cities supported by EU Mission Cities. This is reflected in the SECAP, Energy Atlas, and County Climate Resilience and Adaptation Plan, as well as several adaptation-based projects.

5.5 Meetings with Super User during 2023 and 2024

CMCC is leading the engagement of regions involved in the EU [Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change](#)²⁵ and assist them in demonstrating how seamless climate predictions can support their efforts in improving climate risk assessment and designing transformative adaptation strategies. CMCC actively participates in various regional demonstrators of accelerated climate adaptation (e.g., [DESIRMED](#)²⁶ and [ARCADIA](#)²⁷) and collaborates with several regions that have enrolled in the Mission and signed the Mission Charter. Additionally, CMCC spearheads the development of the regional climate risk assessment framework and toolbox ([CLIMAAX](#)²⁸) and innovative insurance solutions (such as [PIISA](#)²⁹). Since the proposal preparation phase of ASPECT, CMCC has developed a close relationship with the Emilia Romagna region in Northeast Italy. Emilia Romagna is one of the most vulnerable Italian regions to climate change, yet it stands out as a leader in the innovation of climate services. This region is actively advancing climate adaptation strategies and integrating cutting-edge climate prediction tools to mitigate risks and enhance resilience. Previously, within the context of the [CLARA](#)³⁰ H2020 project, the region developed and made operational a climate service estimating irrigation demand based on seasonal forecasts. While the Emilia Romagna region spearheads the involvement of Mission Adaptation regions, it also serves as a pilot application for several other regions, including Lombardy and Sardinia in Italy, and the Zilina region in Slovakia. These regions, which joined the Mission later, are currently in the exploration stage regarding climate prediction knowledge products. Emilia Romagna participated in the ASPECT User Forum events, presenting the application context and series of requirements. A series of follow-up meetings, involving other ASPECT partners such as SMHI, were held with the regional environment agency and the self-governing regional administration. These meetings aimed to elaborate on the opportunities to explore the added value of climate predictions and the ensuing climate services.

Regular quarterly meetings are held with the regional administration, regional environment agency, and river basin (district) authority to explore the data products produced by the ASPECT project, refine the use specifications, and co-design the revised and newly developed climate services. The insights from these data and pilot-driven dialogues are used to design the optimal way of accessing the climate forecasts and developing interfaces to

²⁵

https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe/adaptation-climate-change_en

²⁶ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101112972>

²⁷ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101112737>

²⁸ <https://www.climaax.eu/>

²⁹ <https://piisa-project.eu/>

³⁰ <https://www.clara-project.eu/>

ensure compatibility with existing data management systems. These systems are used to produce climate atlases and bulletins, derive the extreme climate indices of interest, and deliver the information to downstream users such as Water Boards and utilities.

5.6 Informing the co-design of the governance case study

The EU Mission case study, led by CMCC, focuses on the strategic use of climate knowledge for regional risk assessment and adaptation strategies, and creating enabling conditions for the development of regional climate resilience. In a broader sense, this includes a comparison of the initialised climate predictions covering different forecast horizons (10, 20 or 30 years) with non-initialized climate predictions in terms of the expected near-term changes, as well as the reliability (skill assessment) and uncertainty involved in high-resolution data products, to guide short- to medium-term adaptation efforts. In a narrow sense, it entails developing demonstration pilots that showcase the informational value of climate predictions by translating them into tangible improvements in management practices and resilience. These pilots focus on the priority areas of policy and practice within the Mission Adaptation, such as key community systems including water management and community infrastructure.

For the pilot demonstration, the Emilia Romagna region has chosen to focus on **extreme heat affecting major urban centres** and on **intense convective precipitation events impacting the low-altitude former floodplain areas**, which are now developed for urban and agricultural purposes and depend on artificial drainage. The vulnerability of the latter areas has been revealed during the May 2023 events which caused damage to assets of 9 billion Euro. Furthermore, additional demonstration projects are planned to develop water balance models for the right Apennines tributaries to the Po River. These models aim to address the intermittent river flow, which threatens the water supply for water-intensive sectors. For this application, CMCC and the Regional Environment Agency utilise hydrological modelling suites to simulate river flow and water balance driven by downscaled climate seasonal predictions. This approach aims to extend the already existing operational climate service to cover longer time scales, thereby enhancing the accuracy and usefulness of the climate predictions for managing water resources in the region. Details of the technical specifications for climate information required are shown in Table 5.

SMHI is contributing to the Governance case study through co-development of a research plan with the region Emilia Romagna. The planned work, in WP3, includes the application of event-based dynamical downscaling for recent and future climate up to 30 years ahead. A work plan to focus on specific types of extreme climate events is being developed, with strong candidates including heat waves and extreme precipitation events. The dynamical downscaling method, which SMHI has developed, needs to be adjusted for local conditions (to account for proper model spin up and for efficient detection of the extreme events in the global climate simulations). The ambition is to develop consistent information on how these types of events change in the future for the specific region of the Case Study, which is intended to provide an important component of the prototype climate service.

The Emilia-Romagna Region is subject to a number of meteo-climatic extremes, such as heavy precipitation events causing floods and landslides, intense heat waves causing health problems and increasing mortality, severe convective thunderstorms leaving behind extensive damages to private property and public infrastructure, and even prolonged droughts causing high stress to the Region’s irrigation system and water management. The spatial extent of such extremes is typically smaller than the grid cells of the state-of-the-art operational climate predictions. Therefore, over the years, to assist planning and decision-making by the Emilia-Romagna Region, ARPAE has developed statistical downscaling tools of various degrees of complexity and applied to different climate predictions and projections (e.g. Pavan et al., 2005; Tomozeiu et al., 2002; 2006; 2007). In the framework of WP3, CMCC works closely with ARPAE and contributes to further developing such statistical downscaling tools through new approaches (e.g., analogues/ML combined with sub-sampling) and applied to innovative multi-annual predictions produced in ASPECT and/or to decadal predictions, which emerge as central for climate adaptation but have never used operationally by the Region. In this work, downscaling of extremes, particularly heatwaves and heavy precipitation events, will receive a special focus. Such advancements will improve the value and the usability of the downscaled products offered operationally by ARPAE. Further interacting with the Emilia-Romagna officials and with ARPAE (an iterative process), CMCC narrows down the different possibilities to a single, well-defined task with specific expected benefits, taking into consideration the Region's vulnerability and needs, as well as the limitations imposed and the opportunities offered by the climate predictions.

CMCC is also developing a suite of climate hazard and composite risk indices tailored for application at the regional level. This includes operational indices focused on single hazards, such as the Standardised Precipitation Evapotranspiration Index (SPEI), which integrates precipitation and evapotranspiration data to capture the influence of temperature on drought conditions. The Actuaries Climate Index is used to provide a data-driven, quantitative assessment of climate trends by analysing key indicators that reflect changes in extreme weather events. The suite also includes a subnational INFORM Climate Composite Index, part of the [INFORM Risk](https://drmkc.jrc.ec.europa.eu/inform-index/INFORM-Risk)³¹ family, which aggregates climate vulnerability, exposure, and adaptive capacity to offer a nuanced view of climate risks at local levels. These tools support regional climate adaptation efforts by providing insights into climate hazards and vulnerabilities.

Table 5. Specifications and levels of climate information required by the Governance case study.

Decision-Making:
The regional and local climate risk assessments promoted by the Mission adaptation are vital for collective decision-making on how to adapt to climate risks, prioritise goals and visions, and coordinate adaptation processes across various aspects of community living. The focus is on ensuring the prosperity and resilience of communities and the safety and integrity of the environment in which they reside. They contribute to informing and guiding decision-making across many policy areas such as health, public safety, disaster

³¹ <https://drmkc.jrc.ec.europa.eu/inform-index/INFORM-Risk>

management, food safety, environmental protection, financial regulation, critical infrastructure and provision of essential services.			
Specifications			
Location/Region:	Emilia Romagna and other regions in Italy and across Europe, including Lombardy, Zilina, Lower Austria, Skane and Krapina-Zagorje	Target Period:	annual and sub-annual disaggregation (seasons, months)
		Spatial Resolution:	ideally 5 x 5 km or lower
Lead time (how much in advance should the prediction be available):	- decadal for the next 20-30 years - sub-seasonal (3-12 months) and seasonal advancing existing climate services	Frequency (how often the info should be updated):	- decadal forecasts updated every 1-3 years - seasonal forecasts updated once a month prior the irrigation season
Levels of climate information			
Climate-related variables:	- min, max, ave hourly and daily 2m temperature, - hourly and daily precipitation, - Instantaneous 10m wind gust, 10m v-component of wind, - mean sea level pressure, - convective snowfall	Climate-related indicators:	standardised ETCCDI (Expert Team on Climate Change Detection and Indices) climate extreme indices
Risk-informed hazard indicators	Standardised Precipitation Index (SPI), Standardised Precipitation Evapotranspiration Index (SPEI), Streamflow Drought Index (SDI)	Risk indices:	Actuaries Climate Risk Index (ACRI) INFORM Climate

6 Disaster Response during Extreme Events

6.1 Summary of Super User Decision Making Context

The British Red Cross (BRC) is a National Society which sits under the International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies (IFRC). To support individuals and communities to prepare for, respond to and recover from disasters, societies within the IFRC are working towards moving from being emergency response to emergency management organisations. Climate predictions across the timescales of ASPECT have the potential to support this transition by providing insight into potential impacts from extreme weather and the risks associated with climate change, helping responding units to procure, allocate and distribute appropriate resources to people in need.

Engagement with the BRC has primarily been with the UK Climate Adaptation Lead, with additional engagement activities with the Climate Adaptation Group, experienced emergency responders, and the BRC strategic insights team. The Met Office also attended the IFRC Community of Practice event on Heatwaves in the Red Cross and Red Crescent Europe Region. This wide engagement with BRC and IFRC members has provided substantive information about the Super User need.

Emergency responders currently desire more accessible seasonal climate information, available together with vulnerability data to aid seasonal planning and preparedness. However, at a strategic level, the BRC is particularly interested in understanding how future climate information can inform decisions around the procurement and prioritisation of appropriate resources for contingency planning over the next 5-10 years. As the climate changes, the frequency of extreme weather and climate events in the UK is expected to increase, resulting in a greater demand for BRC support. During previous heat events, some regions have reported being depleted of resources after 3 – 4 days. If heat waves become longer, or occur closer together, the BRC may have to change how they respond to these events to avoid running out of supplies. In addition, the intensity of some extreme events, including extreme heat events, is expected to change which may impact the type of resources the BRC might need to procure. Understanding what these extreme events could look like in the future, as well as understanding whether the spatial pattern of events may change, will help the BRC to prioritise the allocation of both resources and volunteers. The need to transition from emergency response to emergency management is driven by the understanding that climate change is increasing the number of extreme weather-related disasters seen around the world and is additionally a ‘threat multiplier’, with extreme weather and climate hazards exacerbating other disasters that the BRC, and other IFRC Societies, respond to.

6.2 User needs from British Red Cross

Engagement to date has predominantly been with, or facilitated by, **Dr Ellie Murtagh, UK Climate Adaptation Lead** at the British Red Cross between January and September 2024. After initial discussions with Dr Murtagh, the Met Office team attended a session of the BRC UK Climate Adaptation group in January 2024, gaining valuable insights from BRC staff and long-standing volunteers. Following an introduction to the ASPECT project, discussion focused on understanding how weather and climate information is currently used, any barriers to use and what hazards currently cause problems for BRC operations. Responders cited extreme high temperatures resulting in impacts such as overheating in personal protective equipment, the reduced efficacy of BRC’s specialised fleet, as well as an increased demand for their services to help support the National Health Service and vulnerable populations. In addition, extreme weather events were considered to pose compounding impacts during the BRC’s response to non-weather-related incidents, such as overheating in evacuation shelters. Other weather and climate hazards, including flooding and cold temperatures also impact BRC’s operations, particularly those that require the organisation of rest centres.

Attendees were asked about what weather and climate information they would like to have access to in an ideal world. The outputs of this discussion can largely be summarised into the categories in Table 6:

Table 6. Summary of user requirements as a 'wish list' gathered from engagement with the BRC

Communication	Seasonal	Decadal -> Climate
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One stop shop for existing weather and climate information • Community resources and targeted education • Data layered with population, vulnerability, and recent impacts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seasonal extreme weather predictions • Localised warning system for extreme weather that will directly impact the need for emergency response and our ability to respond 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand climate risk: combine information about vulnerability and physical hazard to prioritise resources • Visualisation of risk down to neighbourhood level • Consistency across UK • 5 – 10 year plan for buildings, vehicles and workwear

Engagement with the **BRC strategic insights** team focused on how information on **vulnerability** must be combined with hazard data to guide decision-making, to support the most vulnerable. This team provides both rapid insights on operational timescales as well as strategic insights that feed into BRC seasonal plans. For example, this team communicates the current and projected state of **El Niño** and what this might mean for UK weather to BRC staff and volunteers, highlighting that information about wider driving conditions can be directly useful for seasonal preparedness. Further support on seasonal to decadal timescales to tailor this communication is likely to be beneficial, for example, the inclusion of **additional climate drivers** relevant to the UK such as the North Atlantic Oscillation. This team is also starting to consider **longer term adaptation planning** and how they can best support BRC local teams to determine where interventions will be most impactful. Not only does this

require information about how climate hazards are evolving but also where the most vulnerable people and community assets are and will be in the future. In addition, understanding the vulnerability of transport and energy networks is important to determine how weather and climate events might impact the ability of BRC staff and volunteers to be deployed. There may be opportunities to work with the BRC insights team to co-develop appropriate vulnerability datasets, potentially making use of the UK Shared Socio-economic Pathways to provide robust information on **risk** ([Merkle et al. 2023](#)).

Further discussion with an established **emergency responder** provided insight into how seasonal information could be used as a communications tool. For example, this individual felt that advanced warning of an increased period of risk of the need to respond to a particular type of event in their region would help mentally prepare responders. In addition, this information could help team leaders to prepare responders, for example by providing information on how to stay safe in hot weather conditions when responding to emergencies. Current responder uniforms and PPE were cited as a particular problem in hot weather, especially when responding to housefires. In addition, the functioning (or lack) of air conditioning in BRC vehicles was also considered to be sub-optimal in extreme heat events. Using decadal climate information to understand how extreme heat events might change could help to inform whether adjustments to PPE, uniforms and vehicles are required. Information at this timescale could also be used by the Insights team to inform future procurement, for example of specialised vehicles, as well as support journey and location optimization for the BRC fleet.

6.3 British Red Cross' work and interests

The BRC deploy hundreds of emergency response volunteers during **extreme weather events**, such as windstorms, extreme rainfall and heatwaves, providing practical and emotional support. **Operational response** activities include the use of specialist vehicles to provide emergency supplies as well as support at rest centres. Ahead of an event, volunteers also provide targeted advice to communities and vulnerable people, reducing potential impacts by increasing local resilience. There is potential for weather and climate information over the next year, through to climate timescales, to support the BRC to **strategically plan** for these events, enabling responders to better support people in the UK.

The BRC currently use **daily hazard and flood forecast assessments** to support their operational response in the days leading up to an event, for example creating Situational Reports, liaising with partners and standing up volunteers. **Seasonal outlooks** are also used to inform seasonal operational planning, for example the Met Office 3-month outlook is used by the BRC's Insights team in the production of an insights pack. This pack is provided to the Crisis Response Team to provide an overview of expected risks for the upcoming summer or winter season. These plans vary between regions but generally include activities such as engaging with water companies to procure bottled water, stocking sun hats and sunscreen and providing hot weather briefings to staff and volunteers.

However, emergency responders have suggested more could be done at this timescale, for example identifying the need for further internal guidance and consistent **Seasonal Weather Emergency Protocol** (SWEP) for heat. The BRC are keen to expand work in this area via an **Early Action Protocol for Heat** which would enable access of the Disaster Response

Emergency Fund administered by the IFRC. The IFRC mandates that these protocols are produced in collaboration with National Hydromet agencies to determine thresholds and triggers for action.

Some BRC emergency responders suggested **regional seasonal outlooks** would help to mentally prepare responders for a period of increased risk of heat, cold or flood events, as well as enable team leaders to proactively refresh their team on how best to respond to different types of events. Responders also communicated that they would find **higher resolution** information on **seasonal extremes** useful. It is important in user interaction that there is an effort made to manage the Super User expectations from ASPECT, as we understand that it is unlikely that this need will be met during the ASPECT project due to little skill in regional seasonal information for the UK (personal communication from ASPECT colleagues).

6.4 Wider context and challenges around climate information for humanitarian and disaster response

The International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies (IFRC) is composed of 192 National Societies, 160,000 local units and 14 million volunteers ([IFRC 2020](#)). These societies are committed to reducing the impact of disasters, including from weather and climate events, while protecting the health and safety of their staff and volunteers. Extreme weather events not only create challenging conditions in their own right but can also complicate the humanitarian response to non-weather and climate related disasters, particularly when large numbers of people need to be relocated or temporarily sheltered.

Climate change has already increased the frequency and severity of extreme weather events such as droughts, heatwaves, and extreme precipitation in many parts of the world ([IPCC 2021](#)), resulting in greater impacts as well as reducing the recovery time between events ([IPCC, 2023](#)). This trend is expected to continue as the climate warms, even if global warming is limited to 1.5°C, putting increasing pressure on the disaster response effort ([IPCC 2018](#), [IFRC 2019](#)). The translation of an extreme weather or climate event into a disaster is influenced by the exposure and vulnerability of individuals and communities, which in turn is often determined by non-climate factors such as economic development and access to resources ([IFRC 2019](#)). Understanding how the characteristics of weather and climate hazards may change is only one part of the picture - to build resilience and lessen the impact of extreme events climate education, adaptation and preparedness must be targeted at the most vulnerable groups. Identifying who these vulnerable groups are, where they are located and how this might change under different socioeconomic pathways poses another challenge for understanding future risk.

Seasonal forecast information has been shown to provide some skill in identifying periods of extreme weather. For example, ahead of the Pakistan floods in 2022, seasonal forecast outlooks suggested 'above-normal precipitation' with the potential for 'flash flooding in hill torrents' and 'urban flooding' in some regions ([Dunstone et al. 2023](#)). However, these forecasts, as with most currently available seasonal forecast products, were not tailored to provide insight into the likelihood of impactful extremes. Understanding the relationship between forecast weather events and the potential impacts is crucial for providing actionable information to decision makers across disaster response organisations. The development of

this information into tailored skillful forecasts would enable disaster response organisations to increase their anticipatory action, for example releasing funding and initiate volunteer and resource allocation before disasters occur ([Dunstone et al. 2023](#), [IFRC et al. 2022](#)). However, for the BRC case study, skill over the UK is limited and higher resolution seasonal information, or information around seasonal extremes, may not be possible.

Decadal projections have also been developed to provide insight into decision-making at longer, multi-year, timescales. Recent developments in this field have explored changes in the frequency and intensity of extreme temperature and rainfall events, with skill being demonstrated across most land regions, particularly for temperature extremes ([Delgado-Torres et al. 2023](#)). However, impact relevant metrics at a spatial scale meaningful for planning are not yet available to support disaster management. The aspirations of the ASPECT project to provide spatially downscaled, seamless climate information using user-relevant climate metrics and indices would help to support disaster management decisions on seasonal to decadal timescales.

6.5 Super User decisions on different time scales

As well as more frequent extreme weather and climate events, the IFRC are seeking to prepare for unprecedented extremes ([IFRC 2019](#)). In particular, National Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies are being asked to **outline plans to improve their response to extreme heat**. Through their UK Climate Adaptation Work Programme, the BRC are currently developing internal adaptation plans to ensure their service is resilient to these future changes. The BRC are also developing plans to enable them to continue to support communities to adapt to a changing climate. Actions to date largely focus on communication and capacity building as well as income generation to support the implementation of new adaptation projects, some of which will focus specifically on **heat**.

Previous extreme heat events in Europe have led to a large number of excess deaths. For example, over 70,000 excess deaths were attributed to the European 2003 heatwave and over 60,000 during the recent 2022 heatwave ([Ballester et al. 2023](#)). In the UK, the highest temperatures are typically experienced in the **south-east** and this is expected to continue to be the case as the climate warms ([Kennedy-Asser et al. 2022](#)). Therefore this region will be a **priority for higher resolution seasonal to decadal climate information**. However, if combined heat hazards, such as humidity and heat events are taken into account, the **south west** may experience the greatest increase in risk at longer timescales, under a warming scenario of 3°C ([Kennedy-Asser et al. 2022](#)). **Socio-economic factors** exacerbate the risk of heat on health, combining spatial hazard information with exposure and vulnerability information will help the BRC to identify **future hotspots of risk**.

The BRC responds to weather-related disasters caused by other hazards, such as windstorms and extreme rainfall, and so climate information around these hazards would be an additional useful output to the Super User by WPs 1-3. However, the ASPECT case study developed in WP4 will focus on **extreme high temperatures and heatwave events**.

Decisions that could be informed by **seasonal forecasts** include:

- Advertising fixed term contracts ahead of particularly high-risk seasons

- The procurement of equipment and supplies
- Delivery of training for staff and volunteers
- Increased communication with partners such as local councils and local resilience forums.

However, it is currently unclear how **certain** these forecasts would need to be in order for them to be proactively used by BRC in their decision-making process. Anecdotal experience suggests **strategic support** is a larger driver than certainty in the decision-making process, therefore it is very important to generate buy-in throughout BRC.

In addition, seasonal information could be **better communicated** to local teams and responders to prepare them for the season ahead. For example, team leaders could use the information in the seasonal forecast to proactively provide refreshers on responding to hot weather conditions. This information would be particularly valuable if it were **specific to the BRC regions, or potentially even higher resolution**. However, it is recognized that this may not be possible for the UK due to the limited skill in seasonal predictions and the challenges of seasonal prediction at such high resolution.

It is therefore likely that the climate service work for this case study will predominantly focus (at least initially) on the **decadal to climate timescale**.

To best support individuals and communities now and in the future, the BRC need to understand:

- Where volunteers need to be recruited,
- Where emergency vehicles should be located,
- What cooling equipment needs to be procured,
- What protective equipment and workwear are most suitable.

Understanding how the **frequency and severity of extremes** might change over the next **5-10 years** will inform whether new or different types of equipment and workwear might be required to respond to events and will support funding applications for responding to future extreme heat events. In addition, combining information at longer **20-30 year** timescales with vulnerability data will help to identify where **pockets of risk** are evolving as the climate changes, which will inform BRC's longer term strategy for managing extreme weather events.

6.6 Meetings with Super User during 2024

A priority for the BRC is having easily accessible weather and climate information that can be used by response managers and volunteers to inform their plans. Further user engagement with the Super User throughout the ASPECT climate service prototype development will enable WP4 to provide weather and climate information in an appropriate format. So far, engagement has included:

- BRC engagement in the ASPECT User Forum in January 2024
- Meetings with UK Climate Adaptation Lead approximately monthly during 2024.
- Meeting with BRC UK Climate Adaptation Group in January and July 2024

- Additional meetings with experienced emergency responder and vulnerability team at BRC
- Attendance at IFRC Community of Practice event in May 2024 on Heatwaves in the Red Cross and Red Crescent Europe Region
- Attendance at British Red Cross ‘Preparing for extreme heat in London’ workshop in October 2024

We are planning additional engagement in the future with the IFRC to provide further information which will inform potential scalability of the case study. In particular, there has been a key route for engagement identified via the International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies Technical Reference Group for Climate Action – Europe Region, which is currently chaired by the Spanish Red Cross and co-chaired by the British Red Cross.

6.7 Specific climate hazard information for the BRC case study

Potential indicators are continuing to be scoped with the BRC (Table 7) but the following indicators have been identified as interesting to explore (**priority indicators shaded**). A list of specifications is also given in Table 8, with supporting information on England Heat Health Alerts provided in Table 9.

Table 7. Potential indicators for exploration in the BRC case study.

Timescale	Indicator
Seasonal	Monthly average of daily maximum and minimum temperature
Seasonal	Monthly average of daily maximum humidex (combined temperature and humidity index)
Seasonal	Number of days over a threshold (similar level of skill as prediction of seasonal mean but maybe framed in a more impactful way?)
Multi-annual to decadal	5 year average summer mean and maximum 5-day average temperatures
Multi-annual to decadal	5 year average summer mean and maximum 5-day average humidex (combined temperature and humidity index)
Multi-annual to decadal	Monthly, seasonal or annual heatwave frequency & duration (UK heatwave definitions & other informative thresholds e.g. 25, 30, 35, 40, 45). (Similar approach to Delgado-Torres et al. 2023)
Multi-annual to decadal	Monthly, seasonal or annual number of heat health alert days (using indicative thresholds - see Table 4 below)
Multi-annual to decadal	Monthly, seasonal or annual % of days when maximum temperature > 90th daily percentile (Delgado-Torres et al. 2023)

Multi-annual to decadal	Seasonal or annual maximum of daily maximum temperature (Delgado-Torres et al. 2023)
Multi-annual to decadal	Average heat wave cumulative area (thresholds of 25, 28, 30, 3 days, min area 400km ²) (Beckett & Sanderson, 2021)

Table 8. Specifications and levels of climate information required for supporting action plans for buildings, vehicles, equipment and resources for the BRC case study.

Decision: 5-10 year action plans for buildings, vehicles, equipment, resources			
<p>Understanding how the frequency and severity of hot temperature days and heatwaves are expected to change over the next 5-10 years will inform whether new or different types of equipment and workwear will be required to respond to events and will support funding applications for responding to future extreme heat events.</p> <p>Combining changing hazard and vulnerability information will help to identify hotspots of risk which will inform BRC's response management strategy.</p>			
Specifications			
Region	UK wide. Regions can be prioritized for high resolution information if necessary (e.g. South-East England).	Target period	Focus on the extended summer season (May – Sept) and typical summer (Jun - Aug). Decadal to climate timescales, with a particular emphasis on the 5 to 10 year timescale.
Forecast type:	Decadal predictions Climate projections	Spatial Resolution	Hazard information at neighbourhood level is desirable. Spatial resolution up to the highest resolution of the current UK Climate Projections (2.2 km) may be more realistic. Regional information (BRC regions).
Lead time:	Still to be worked out with BRC.	Frequency	Still to be worked out with BRC.
Levels of climate information			
Climate-related variables	- Daily maximum temperature - Daily minimum temperature - Daily mean temperature	Climate-related indicators	Number of high temperature days and heatwaves at each model grid box per month (or season) and year (using UK heatwave definitions ³² which vary regionally between 25 and 28 °C). Also using lower and higher thresholds for scalability across Europe (e.g. 25, 30, 35, 40, 45 °C).

³² [metoffice.gov.uk/weather/learn-about/weather/types-of-weather/temperature/heatwave](https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/weather/learn-about/weather/types-of-weather/temperature/heatwave)

	Humidity variables may also be useful for exploring heat stress. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Daily maximum humidity - Daily mean humidity 		Number of England Heat Health Alerts ³³ triggered per month (or season) and year (Table 5). Number of short duration (3 day) and long duration (2+ weeks) heatwave events. Maximum and average heatwave / hot spell duration per month (or season) and year.
Risk-informed hazard indicators		Risk indices	WP4 will work with BRC to incorporate exposure and vulnerability information to calculate risk.

Table 9. England Heat Health Alerts

Region	Level	% inc. mortality	Max T (°C)	Night T
London	V.L	NA	<28	95th percentile
	L	10%	28-31.9	95th percentile
	M	20%	32-39.9	95th percentile
	H	50%	>40	95th percentile
All	V.L	NA	<27	95th percentile
	L	10%	28-29.9	95th percentile
	M	20%	30-37.9	95th percentile
	H	50%	>38	95th percentile

³³ [metoffice.gov.uk/weather/warnings-and-advice/seasonal-advice/heat-health-alert-service](https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/weather/warnings-and-advice/seasonal-advice/heat-health-alert-service)

6.8 Informing co-design of the disaster response case study

Met Office user engagement with BRC has revealed that to best support individuals and communities now and in the future, the BRC is looking to understand how climate may affect where volunteers need to be recruited, where emergency vehicles should be located, and what protective equipment, medicines and workwear are most suitable. The BRC is particularly interested in acquiring more information about the projected increased frequency of heatwaves and hot summers in the future in the UK that might create a risk to their future operations. Therefore our case study is being designed to study heatwaves, and understanding how the frequency and severity of heat extremes might change over the next 5-10 years and beyond (e.g., at different global warming levels) and how these extremes may impact on health. Provision of this information through a prototype climate service will inform whether new or different types of equipment and workwear might be required to respond to events and will support funding applications for responding to future extreme heat events.

In addition, combining information at longer 20-30 year timescales with vulnerability data will help to identify where pockets of risk are evolving as the climate changes, which will inform BRC's longer term strategy for managing extreme weather events. The plan is for the Met Office to collaborate with the BRC insights team to co-develop appropriate vulnerability datasets, potentially making use of the UK Shared Socio-economic Pathways (derived from the IPCC global Shared Socio-economic Pathways) to provide robust information on risk. As the question of how heat extremes will affect population health and emergency response will be of interest to disaster responders across Europe and worldwide, we envisage high potential scalability from our prototype development.

University of Oxford (UOxf) have started to plan exploratory work merging seasonal and the novel multi-annual timescale predictions from ASPECT into information which would help BRC user need on seasonal to multi-annual timescales. They plan to perform this work across Europe, so it is envisaged to be potentially very useful to inform scalability of the case study to other parts of Europe. Their work will consider both temperature and humidity to assess the multivariate aspect of heat stress.

7 Humanitarian (anticipatory action to prevent malnutrition)

7.1 Summary of Super User Decision Making Context

In general, the needs of the humanitarian sector are related to all the time scales included in ASPECT. Decisions for which climate information can be useful to support SCI's decision making are included in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Humanitarian decision-making processes at different timescales, highlighting those decisions that cut across scales in red. Image presented by Save the Children during the meeting in BSC's premises.

7.2 Introduction to Save the Children

One of the ASPECT's Super User for the humanitarian sector is Save the Children International (SCI), a child rights organisation working to reach every last child through education, health and nutrition, and to implement child protection programs in development and humanitarian settings across 120 countries. The main goals of SCI are:

- **Healthy start in life:** children will have equitable access to and use quality essential health and nutrition services.
- **Safe back to school & learning:** children will achieve wellbeing and learning outcomes.
- **Live free from violence:** children affected by conflict and gender-based violence are protected.
- **Safety nets & resilient families:** Children will be lifted out of poverty.

SCI's overall strategy recognizes that the 'climate crisis' directly affects children around the world and is the greatest threat to their survival, learning and protection. Without intervention, today's children will bear the greatest burden, especially those living in the most vulnerable regions in the world.

SCI is the first child-focused humanitarian and development NGO accredited to the UN's Green Climate Fund (GCF). The GCF brings SCI huge opportunities to support national governments at scale to respond and adapt effectively to climate change. The organisation has a \$280m GCF project pipeline that includes four Health and Nutrition programmes. They also work alongside a broad range of local, national, and international partners, including the International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies (IFRC), START Network, and regional and national hydro meteorological centres, among others, to develop and extend anticipatory action (AA) for a range of hazards across regions. SCI aims to support communities and local actors in identifying risks of weather and climate impacts for children before they happen and address these risks through preparedness, AA, disaster risk reduction and longer-term climate change adaptation. They have been working for years on monitoring hazards and risk levels at the global level and with communities as well as to take action ahead of crises.

The work of SCI is guided by the 'Climate Crisis Framework for Action' and 'Accelerating Action on Climate with Health Benefits' Strategy' which take a systems-based, multisectoral approach to address climate, health and equity. For example, early warnings can be linked to actions on nutrition and food insecurity. By combining health, nutrition and hunger as well as livelihood efforts, SCI is interested in developing an early warning system that integrates data from a range of sources to provide evidence for decision-makers on how climate change impacts household food and nutrition security and identify at-risk households. The aim is that this tool contributes to increasing the global understanding of the relationship between drought and health and nutrition outcomes and informs cash transfers or other programs to improve nutrition for children and families.

Tools that help SCI quantify possible climate risks for children and families may enable them to improve planning for risks to children at several levels. These benefits would contribute to their journey to shift power to national and local organisations so that outcomes for children and their communities are more timely, appropriate, and effective. In the longer run, improved weather and climate risk information targeted to children can inform child rights situation analyses developed in countries the organisation works in, as well as partnerships and policy objectives around climate change adaptation and disaster risk management and reduction.

7.3 Super User attitude towards probabilistic information and expectations

SCI aims to transform the aid system to act earlier and smarter, preventing or reducing the impact of humanitarian crises on children and communities now and in the future. With this aim, they have started to use a wide range of climate services to inform decision-making in adaptation for humanitarian and development programs. Their climate and health programmatic strategy focuses on systems approaches for climate action. For at-risk communities, SCI actively communicates weather and climate information and supports improved impact-based forecasting. They have a growing network of climate technical experts in all regions and contexts, in addition to:

- Strong expertise in developing proposals for accessing GCF funding, to health and AA.

- A dedicated Context Analysis and Foresight Unit (CAFU), providing their teams with tailored analyses for strategic decision-making.
- Regional advisors focusing on long-term climate trends and additional technical expertise.
- Increasing partnerships on climate, including with the Intergovernmental Authority on Development (IGAD) Climate prediction and Application Center (ICPAC), and national hydromet offices to ensure preparedness and early action are informed by accurate forecasting and support effective early warning systems.

7.4 Super User decisions related to different time scales

Medium to long term climate change **impacts due to heatwaves and desertification on food production as well as disease outbreaks following floods** may affect child nutrition.

In the **short-medium term**, Save the Children International can develop climate-smart nutrition initiatives.

In the **longer term**, drought conditions may impact the choice of crops to be planted in February in the following years, meaning that if a drought period is expected, it is better to select crops with lower water demand. In addition, drought conditions in the long term may exacerbate crop depletion and desertification, therefore impacting the decision of families to migrate (usually to urban settings).

Information about **long term climate trends** and their impact on nutrition can help SCI to produce advocacy reports and policy papers to raise awareness on the potential impacts of climate change on families and children. It can also influence governmental health decisions and planning in their Nationally Determined Contributions (NDC) and National Adaptation Plans (NAPs), which are the processes by which countries plan for and communicate their mitigation and adaptation goals and strategies to the global community.

In ASPECT, we will focus on a case study in Africa that considers climate information from seasonal to decadal time scales. **The affordability of a nutritious diet has been defined as a proxy for malnutrition** that can be measured with the [Cost of the Diet](#) (CotD) and the [Household Economy Analysis](#) (HEA) indicator (see below), which indicates the income deficit of people. As CotD only provides a snapshot of the situation, a link to the HEA is needed to move to anticipatory and predictive capacity. While the HEA can provide us the future state of income and income gaps for families after a shock to meet basic living condition (survival and livelihood thresholds), the CotD with projected food prices in the future can tell us if the incomes resulting from families coping mechanism is enough to afford nutritious diet for their children. The combination of these 2 tools can help Save the Children quantify this gap and hence decide on the most effective solutions to reduce or close the gap via Anticipated Action (before the crisis occurs).

Livelihood Zoning is the first step in an HEA baseline. It establishes the context in which all further work is done. It is defined as an area within which people share broadly the same

means of production (determining what people can grow or raise) and the same access to markets (where people trade their goods, including labour).

Household Economy Analysis (HEA) framework

HEA was developed in the early 1990s by Save the Children-UK to improve the ability to predict short-term changes in access to food. An understanding of livelihoods is at the heart of HEA – leading to its application beyond emergency food needs. Seasonal information on rainfall, crops, livestock, labour and self-employment, and prices is combined with baseline data to indicate which wealth groups within a population are likely to face food and income deficits. The framework aims to:

- i) quantify the problem allowing a systematic analysis of the predicted effects of a hazard or multiple hazards on household livelihood assets,
- ii) provide a system for comparing poverty levels and prioritizing needs across different areas,
- iii) provide reliable results for large populations,
- iv) point to appropriate responses,
- v) be predictive/anticipatory.

HEA translates a forecasted shock into an economic impact on households' access to food, income and expenditure, and projects households' abilities to meet their food needs and protect their livelihoods. Combined with population data, the analysis provides an estimate of the number of people that will need assistance to protect livelihoods and well-being and prevent hunger, the total food or cash equivalent required and the months when it will be needed. Its ability to quantify impacts and define when households will be impacted renders it an effective tool for triggering and informing anticipatory action.

More information on the HEA and examples can be found in the [Household Economy Analysis for Anticipatory Action Factsheet](#).

Since SCI has access to various sources of socio-economic and health information in Africa, the following steps have been defined in order to identify the most suitable country to focus the ASPECT case study on, taking into account the availability of information for model validation as well as the quality of state-of-the-art climate predictions for the area, period, and variables of interest.

Next steps:

1. Share the livelihood zones for each potential African country (administrative boundaries) and data on HEA and the Cost of the Diet. Check which countries have the longest time series for HEA (SCI) - *completed*.
2. Find out what input (climate) variables go into HEA's calculation and evaluation, and how skill information is used (SCI)
3. Check in which areas there is information about malnutrition, food security indicators and diseases available (SCI)
4. Analyse the windows of opportunity for climate variables/indicators in the different livelihood zones (BSC)

7.5 Meetings with Super User during 2024

Engagement with Save the Children International has been carried out by BSC. The first

meeting was held online in early 2024 and, after a brief introduction of the ASPECT project by BSC, SCI presented the activities conducted by the organisation and talked generally about the use of climate information in the humanitarian sector. In a second online meeting, both organisations discussed the criteria for the selection of the case study, the type of data available (regarding both climate and impact data), and the time scales of interest for SCI. They also defined the terms of collaboration between SCI and ASPECT (this was important since SCI is not part of the project consortium). In June 2024, an in-person full-day meeting took place at the BSC headquarters. With the objective to define a specific case study to jointly work on, the meeting included several presentations on the overall work carried out by both SCI and BSC as well as a description of the concept of malnutrition (a problem to tackle by SCI), how climate change affects it, and the importance of anticipatory action to minimise the impact. Some specifications, a work plan with the next steps, and a timeline for the case study were also agreed. Although this case study is located outside of Europe, it focuses on disaster preparedness in a region of European interest, aligning with the project's objectives. SCI also focuses its efforts in other conflict areas in Eastern Europe, where lessons learned in Africa can be applied. In addition, it can be a learning case for Europe, since similar problems may arise due to the extremely hot temperatures climate change may bring, and the potential compounding impacts of increasing migrants and conflict.

After the selection of SCI as a new Super User in ASPECT, interactions with the organisation included an initial meeting to agree on their official introduction during the second ASPECT User Forum, where they presented their activities and talked generally about the use of climate information in the humanitarian sector.

Meeting zero (12 April 2024): Get to know each other. Discuss the type of data available, understand the period of the case study and what happens afterwards, and define criteria to consider to identify potential case studies.

After the User Forum, an online meeting between BSC and SCI followed on the 12th of April 2024, where both organisations discussed the criteria to consider for the selection of the case study collaboration, the type of data available, and to understand what are the time scales of interest of SCI.

Meeting #1 (10 June 2024): Start the case study definition (decisions that cut across different time scales), purpose, and identification of information needed.

A full-day meeting was held at the headquarters of the Barcelona Supercomputing Center (Figure 11). The agenda with the discussion points covered during the meeting is included below:

Time (CEST)	Discussion points
9:00-9:10	Introduction: roundtable, presentation of participants and agenda of the day
9:10-9:50	Presentation of SCI work on climate and health (Save, 20 min) Presentation of BSC overall work, emphasizing ASPECT (BSC, 20 min)
9:50-10:10	Presentation of the concept of malnutrition and conceptual framework of the impact of climate change on malnutrition (Save)
10:10-11:10	Presentation of the case study project, overall expected outcome, and the model we plan to develop (Save)
11:10-11:30	Coffee break
11:30-13:00	Discussion around data gaps, gap on health element (disease, mortality) and relationship to climatic shock, and possible collaboration with BSC
13:00-14:00	Lunch break
14:00-15:30	Agreement of the project and purpose of collaboration. Fill in case study tables.
15:30-16:30	Draft workplan, timeline, next meeting, milestones, etc.
(extra time)	AOB

The Save the Children International team was formed by:

- *Revati Phalkey* – Global Health and Nutrition Director and Save the Children’s lead for this work. Offers a wide range of technical expertise, including extensive research experience in climate change and health.
- *Hannah Richards* – Health Innovations Manager. Manages health and nutrition innovations and partnerships and will provide programme management support to the case study.
- *Christophe Belperron* – West & Central Africa Senior Climate Resilience Advisor. He contributes to the technical expertise in climate resilience and leads the project proposed as the primary case study for EU ASPECT.
- *Emma Visman* – Senior Advisor for Humanitarian Climate Crisis Unit. Lends her technical expertise in climate and how we can use climate data to improve anticipatory action and response.
- *Dom Kniveton* – Professor of Climate Science and Society. Has joined Save the Children to lead a 3-year research grant to understand the impact of climate change events on neonatal health, including nutrition. Highly related to the proposed case study (attending the meeting online due to health issues).

Figure 11. Save the Children and Barcelona Supercomputing Center teams during the meeting in Barcelona on June 10, 2024

Meeting #2 (Nov-Dec 2024): after some restructuring on the Super User's side, BSC will meet the new team at Save the Children, also involving experts in HEA/Cost of the Diet indicators, for case study follow-up.

Next (Jan 2025-Dec 2026): regular meetings every 4 months to follow-up on the case study, including topics such as the case study analysis with new seamless climate information and the assessment of socio-economic added value of climate information.

7.6 Decisions for Humanitarian sector case study

The decisions considered in the humanitarian sector case study include the definition of appropriate AA measures, both relevant from the seasonal to decadal time scales. A description of the technical specifications required for each of the decisions is included in Table 9 below. AA is acting ahead of a predicted hazard to prevent or reduce the impacts on communities before they fully unfold. AA can be used interchangeably with 'Early Action', which SCI has championed for years as an effective approach to slow-onset crises, before households revert to coping strategies that may harmfully impact livelihoods and children's well-being.

Table 9. Specifications and levels of climate information required for supporting anticipatory action

Decision-Making: Define appropriate anticipatory action measures			
<p>The affordability of a nutritious diet has been defined as a proxy for malnutrition, which can be measured with the Household Economy Analysis (HEA) indicator, which indicates the income deficit of people, and the Cost of the Diet.</p>			
Specifications			
Location/Region:	Africa (country tbd)	Target Period:	window of 6 months to 1 year or more
Forecast type:	Seasonal predictions Decadal predictions	Spatial Resolution:	Livelihood zones
Lead time (how much in advance should the prediction be available):	tbd	Frequency (how often the info should be updated):	tbd
Levels of climate information			
Climate-related variables:	Temperature Rain	Climate-related indicators:	Drought
Risk-informed hazard indicators		Risk indices:	Household economy analysis (HEA) Cost of the diet

7.7 Informing co-design of the humanitarian case study

Medium to long-term climate change impacts due to heatwaves and desertification on food production as well as disease outbreaks following floods may affect child nutrition in various developing countries. In the short-medium term, Save the Children International (SCI) can develop climate-smart nutrition initiatives. In the longer term, drought conditions may impact the choice of crops to be planted in the following years, meaning that if a drought period is expected, selecting crops with lower water demand may be a smart choice. In addition, drought conditions in the long term may exacerbate crop depletion and desertification, therefore impacting the decision of families to migrate (usually to urban settings). In the view of potential hazards exacerbated by climate change, impacts, and SCI's anticipatory action capacity, the initial design of the case study will focus on assessing the forecast quality for seasonal and annual temperature and precipitation, and indicators such as drought conditions. The case study will be located in Africa and will consider climate information from seasonal to decadal time scales. The affordability of a nutritious diet has been defined as a proxy for malnutrition that can be measured with the Cost of the Diet and the Household Economy Analysis (HEA) indicator, indicating the income deficit of people. Since SCI has access to various sources of socio-economic and health information in Africa, we will select the country to focus the case study taking into account the availability of impact information for model validation as well as the quality of state-of-the-art climate predictions for the area, period, and variables of interest.

8. Discussion

This deliverable provides extensive information around each Super User and their decision making context. Here we provide a short discussion considering synergies across case study design and challenges around user engagement to inform the design of the case studies across the Super Users.

When we consider hazards (and related climate variables) required for the case study needs, we must note that the design of the case studies is a combination of some of the Super User requirements and the realistic science-driven understanding about which variables can be assessed for skill usefully in seasonal to decadal predictions, and the future decision making priorities of the Super Users. We acknowledge there are many weather related hazards that can affect different sectors of society, and other hazards are discussed in the user engagement, but the design of the case studies focuses on temperature and precipitation variables. Both temperature and precipitation are important for a range of hazards affecting many sectors of society (e.g., extreme cold, heat, flooding, drought), and therefore consideration of multiple hazards across case studies considering temperature and precipitation extremes will provide a useful foundation for research into the potential of scaling up these case studies to a range of other users (in WP5 of ASPECT).

In the proposed initial case study design outlined here, we have a focus on temperature by considering extreme heat in the disaster response British Red Cross and the governance (Emilia-Romagna region) case studies, and the timing of spring frosts in the viticulture case study. For rainfall, in the viticulture case study, prolonged reduced rainfall leading to drought is considered, whilst extreme rainfall is the focus of the pensions case study and the governance case study (Emilia-Romagna region). The humanitarian Save the Children case study will include both predictions of temperature, rainfall and drought indicators.

We reflect on the challenges faced during the user engagement work. Although all Super Users remain committed to working with the ASPECT project, as is often encountered in research work focused on the development of climate services, they are not all able to provide as much input as might be desirable by the research partners due to constraints on their time for a range of reasons (note only one Super User is part of the consortium, with the others associated with the project on a voluntary basis). Climate services providers, and as such WP4, need to therefore consider carefully when user engagement is beneficial and when users should be involved and to what extent ([Baluenas et al. 2023](#)). Two Super Users have had changes in staff during the initial year of working with them, adding time to develop additional relationships with new contacts.

As it is crucial for continued engagement that we build, rather than deteriorate, relationships with Super Users, we must respect the time limitations of Super Users and work with them to utilise limited time most effectively and for mutual benefit, respecting the boundaries of their domain knowledge and with understanding of their decision making context. It is important that we prioritise relationship building with the appropriate actors in our Super User context, whilst maintaining a flexible approach and realistic expectations in our interactions ([Golding et al. 2023](#), Figure 12). In addition, as a research project, although we cannot change the

timescales of the project, we are focussed on learning from the *process* of co-production and not only the outputs (Golding et al. 2023, Figure 12). It is important that we also continue to make time to draw on leading thinking around the understanding of what co-production means, taking time to appreciate why different actors are participating in the process itself to attempt to overcome the often experienced disconnect between producers of climate knowledge and users (Howarth et al. 2022). In addition, we have been working closely with social scientists in WP5 as part of considering the project user engagement strategy, as it is widely recognised by climate service focussed researchers that the lack of social science input into the development of climate services has historically limited the usefulness of some services (Bruno Soares & Buontempo, 2019).

Figure 12. From Golding et al. (2023) Fig 1. Summary of the key themes relating to a required step change in co-production research for climate resilience

Another challenge faced in the development of this work is a mismatch of expectations amongst consortium partners around the role of Super Users in being able to comment on technical methodological questions across work packages, from the development of the modelling systems, to techniques for seamless climate information. The Super Users of this project are mostly ‘end-users’ of climate services, rather than technical skilled users of climate data, with key contacts for each Super User having little technical background in the direct use of climate model data. Compared to the other Super Users, Emilia-Romagna’s governance stands out due to its representation by the regional environment agency, which possesses advanced technical expertise. Their involvement in the Mission Adaptation initiative has fostered a more direct use of climate data than the other Super Users currently have and a highly developed understanding of local climate risks.

As WP4 are the developers of the climate service prototypes within the ASPECT project, we have reframed the dialogue around the term ‘user’ to provide clarity that WP4 are the users

of data and information from WPs 1, 2 and 3, and Super Users are the users of the climate service prototypes which are being developed by WP4. The need was identified for an internal best practice document to help set expectations and provide clarity on workflows around user engagement particularly regarding the case studies (Code of Conduct document, provided in Annex II). This document was designed by the project coordinators in consultation with WP4 leads, and with input and discussion with other work package leads, to clarify how we should communicate internally within the project to ensure fruitful collaboration with the Super Users across the study cases without overwhelming them with time demands or dialogue at an inappropriate level.

In addition, WP4 also needed to ensure regular communication with other WPs internally to facilitate effective collaboration on the case studies across consortium partners, and provide other WPs with necessary information in a timely manner. Although WP4 meetings are held very regularly throughout the project (every 3 weeks), few members doing underpinning research and method development were attending these meetings in the first year, so a broader approach of creating consortium-wide 'case study meetings', commencing in the second year of the project. There are three each year for each case study, effectively creating 1 extra meeting a month for the consortium, with August, December and January avoided due to holidays, end of year deadlines and preparation for the User Forums and General Assembly. These case study meetings are chaired by case study leads from WP4 but the whole consortium are encouraged to attend, with research development across the consortium related to the case studies presented and discussed. We have also clarified to project partners that they can communicate with case study leads around specific questions needed by email as well as meetings, so that research workflows can be minimally delayed.

In summary, we are cognisant of prior learning from the field of climate services development and related social science, and are developing our approaches to progress our climate service prototype development to align with this research, whilst also working within a project landscape that is diverse with a range of researchers from many disciplines. Whilst this is a strength of the ASPECT project, effective user engagement and co-production both internally and externally is a time consuming and challenging process for all involved.

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Annex I: ASPECT Protocol for Interaction with Super Users

Purpose of this document

This document lists the tasks and topics that will be covered during the first interactions with Super Users in the framework of the ASPECT project. Such interactions will have the objective to understand the Super Users' contexts and identify their information requirements, which will be reported in Milestone 13 on *Provision of requirements of first cohort of Super Users to WPs 1-3* (due month 4) and Milestone 14 on *Provision of requirements of second cohort of Super Users to WPs 1-3* (due month 18).

This document is a rough guide towards the points that will be discussed. It is not ad verbatim script so that case study leads may have a more natural conversation with Super Users and may explore points of interest, both expected and unexpected, as they arise during the conversation.

The case study leads can choose from a list of proposed questions (see below). The most important questions are marked in bold to help the case study leads guide the discussion and, at the same time, collect common information. However, the case study lead should feel free to make a different selection, based on their knowledge, familiarity, and experience with a given Super User.

Overall research parameters

Role	Super Users
Session Duration	Flexible according to Super Users' availability and the final number of questions selected
No of participants	At least 3 (one moderator, one note-taker, one Super User) <i>if there is the possibility that additional staff from the Super User's team join, this is a preferred option</i>
Logistic requirements	Voice or video recording (optional)
Material	Powerpoint presentation (optional)

Discussion structure and timings

N°	Section title	Goals	Priorities	Duration
1	Presentation of the project	Greet and provide a brief overview of the goal of ASPECT Present some general climate-related concepts (use presentation slides) Answer to Super User's questions about presented slides	Medium	30 min

2	Introduction of the Super User	Understand Super User's background and experience with climate data and information. Identify capabilities around weather and climate risk of potential Super User. Discover which information they currently use and if they have some in-house tools	Medium	15 min
3	Probabilistic information and expectations	Understand general attitudes probabilistic information and expectations regarding the results that ASPECT will deliver	Medium	15 min
4	Topic specific questions	Explore needs and motivations regarding adaptation to climate change in the medium and long term Identify Super User decisions that depend on future climate Explore which decisions and adaptation measures are likely to have the greatest impact Added value of seamless climate information vs current climate information	High	45 min
5	Wrap up	Explore additional comments	Low	5 min

Note that all parts of the discussion are equally useful, since they address different needs, so please make sure to cover them all.

Part N° 1 serves to provide some context on the project and introduce and clarify user-relevant climate concepts.

Parts N° 2 and N° 3 help us understand the Super Users' background, their use of climate information, their probabilistic literacy and their expectations regarding the participation in the ASPECT project.

Part N° 4 is the most important part of the interview as it consists of questions that are tightly linked with the climate services to be developed and the added value of seamless information, so please make sure you dedicate enough time to it.

Part N° 5 gives the opportunity to the participant to express any general comment or thoughts they think are important and did not come up during the discussion.

Discussion step by step

1. Presentation of the project

Greet and provide an overview of the main objective(s) of ASPECT and user-relevant climate-related concepts <i>Start recording if applicable</i>	Medium 30 min
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Use the powerpoint presentation to introduce the project and some user-relevant climate related concepts that need to be clear for a good discussion.

Topics covered in the presentation:

- Aim of the project (*skip if the Super User is already familiar with the project*)

- Time horizons of climate predictions (including seasonal predictions, decadal predictions, and climate change projections). Weather features (e.g. extreme events).
- Concept of skill or quality of the predictions
- Layers of information
 - Climate-related variables (e.g. surface temperature, precipitation)
 - Climate-related indicators (e.g. extreme heat, hydrological drought)
 - Risk-informed hazard indicators considering the user vulnerability and adaptation tipping points
 - Risk indices that depend on vulnerability and exposure (depending on users' in-house tools)
- Geographical scale & downscaling: spatial and temporal resolution
- Seamless climate information & added value compared to current (individual) climate information

2. Introduction

Understand Super Users' background and experience with climate data	Medium 15 min
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What is your background? What is your current role/position in the company?

How did you start working in the [x] sector?

What challenges do you have in your day-to-day work?

Can you tell us about projects you have worked on that relate to the use of climate data?

Pros & Cons: What did you like about them? What didn't you like about them?

Did those projects provide you with climate information that you applied? Why/why not?

3. Dealing with probabilities + expectations

Understand general attitudes towards probabilistic information and expectations regarding the project	Medium 15 min
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Where do you check information about climate and how?

How do you use climate information?

How do you download and share the data?

How do you deal with the probabilities, uncertainty and assumptions of the scientific approaches?

What are your experiences, struggles, obstacles with climate data and did you overcome them?

In the working environment, do you have in-house tools that integrate climate information? If so, how?

What do you expect from participating in ASPECT?

How do you think the climate-related information provided will be different from the one you have been using so far?

4. Topic Specific questions

Explore needs and motivations Identify Super User decisions that depend on future climate Explore which decisions are likely to have the greatest impact Added value of seamless vs current climate information	High 45 min
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How will climate change impact your sector/activities?
 What decisions will be affected by climate change?
 How does scientific understanding affect the decisions you make?
 Which stakeholders will be affected/involved?
Is there a need for specific climate information?
What would be relevant climate data for you?

Are there (extreme) weather or climate events that are of particular concern for your sector?

Could you describe how these (extreme) events impact your activities?

Can you think of a recent one?

What data do you hold about the impact on your operations? (can you share it?)

Can you mention 1-2 decisions that you have to make that depend on climate?

Which are the consequences of continuing with BaU in case of unfavourable climate conditions?

What adaptation measures could be required to counteract potential outcomes? Are they in your hands? Who should apply them?

How do you know they work?

Are there exogenous risk factors that should be accounted for?

How do climate policy and adaptation measures fit in the risk assessment?

Are there any ethical and social priorities that should be considered?

5. Wrap up

Explore additional comments	Low 5 min
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Ask if there is any comment or additional information that comes to the Super Users' mind.
 **

Data Requirements Table

It is advised to have one table for each decision

Decision-Making:
Short context description

Specifications		
Location/Region:	Target Period:	
Forecast type:	Spatial Resolution:	
Lead time (how much in advance should the prediction be available):	Frequency (how often the info should be updated):	
Levels of climate information		
Climate-related variables:	Climate-related indicators:	
Risk-informed hazard indicators	Risk indices:	

Annex II: Internal ASPECT Code of Conduct for User Engagement particularly for case studies

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CODE OF CONDUCT FOR CASE STUDY INTERACTIONS IN THE ASPECT PROJECT

This Code of Conduct (CoC) has been implemented to clarify and facilitate the interactions among ASPECT's partners and Super Users in the context of the work developed for the different case studies as well as to provide a set of good practices to be adopted for the smooth development of the project.

Sections contained in this document:

1. Operationalisation of the interactions within the case studies
2. Interactions with the Super Users
3. Interactions with other interested users
4. Good practice for the smooth development of the project

1. Operationalisation of the interactions within the ASPECT case studies

One of the elements that differentiates ASPECT from other projects is that co-production with Super Users is at the backbone of the project developments. This calls for a two-way dialogue among climate information providers and users. Failing to achieve that, has been identified as a risk for not having sufficiently clear results by the end of the project on how forecasts can be used for decision-making.

To avoid this happening, it is important that all WPs are aligned around the different case studies and that technical developments occur in a coordinated manner.

In addition to leading the development of the climate service prototypes, **case study leads in WP4** will be responsible for coordinating the work around each case study, involving:

- Clear definition of specific user needs (i.e. variables or indicators requested, locations, time scales, etc.)
- Ensure that user needs are fulfilled with the outcomes of tasks to be developed under WP1-WP3 and WP6 (this includes selecting, from all the user needs, those that the project will be able to tackle)
- Ensure the coordination among partners and avoid overlap among the technical developments
- Ensure that all other WPs have access to the information they need that relates to the Super Users in order to make progress.

Case study	WP4 case study leads ¹
Agriculture (Codorniu/BSC)	Verónica Torralba/Carlos Delgado/Marta Terrado
Finance (Pension sector/Met Office)	Freya Garry/Dan Bernie
Governance (Emilia-Romagna region/CMCC)	Jaroslav Mysiak / Panos Athanasiadis
Humanitarian (Save the Children/BSC) - new	Verónica Torralba/Carlos Delgado/Marta Terrado
Disaster response during extreme events (British Red Cross/Met Office) - new	Freya Garry/Dan Bernie

2. Interactions with the Super Users

¹ contact details in the [wiki](#)

The engagement and facilitation of the collaboration with the ASPECT Super Users will be centralized in WP4, which includes ASPECT colleagues with both technical and social sciences expertise in the co-production of climate services. Case study leads, who have developed a trust relationship with the Super Users, will therefore act as intermediaries between the developers of climate information (WPs 1-3 and WP6) and the users of this information, facilitating direct interaction where it is beneficial and desired for specific queries that will aid particular methodological developments.

The following channels for other WP colleagues interacting with WP4 case study leads are envisaged:

- **Direct e-mail contact:** to be used for quick feedback.
- **Case study specific meetings organised by case study leads:** the frequency of these meetings will be agreed for each particular case. These meetings will be open to the whole consortium and the information on the connection details and minutes will be made available in the [ASPECT wiki](#).
- **WP4 meetings:** other partners are welcome to join the regular WP4 meetings if they want to discuss specific user-relevant issues more urgently, or to talk to all case study leads together. The WP4 agenda will include a standing agenda item for input into other WP work. WP4 meeting details are available [on the project wiki](#).

WP4 case study leads are in regular contact with Super Users to support WP4 activity as WP4 design climate service prototypes in co-production with Super Users. *In some specific cases*, the option to organise a joint discussion involving other consortium members and the Super Users may be discussed with the WP4 case study leads. An appropriate course of action will be discussed depending on the particular issue at hand (i.e. WPs methodological developments) to make the interactions as efficient as possible for the benefit of ASPECT researchers and Super Users alike. However, be mindful that the time that each Super User uses for the project needs to be respected since most of them are engaging in kind.

Information about the Super Users' requirements will also be delivered at these points in time through the relevant milestones and deliverables:

- **April 2023:** [Provision of requirements of first cohort of superusers to work packages 1, 2 and 3 \(milestone 13\)](#)
- **June 2024:** Identification of additional superusers and provision of requirements of second cohort of superusers to work packages 1, 2 and 3 ([milestone 14](#))
- **December 2024:** Understanding superusers' climate information requirements and decision-making context to inform the co-design of case study specifications ([D4.1](#))

3. Interactions with other interested users

Technical developments in WPs1-3 should consider the broader user needs identified in WP5 activities. The results of technical developments can be showcased through particular user-targeted activities organised under WP5 and WP7 (after the results have been shared within the consortium and for case study relevant findings, the case study leads). These activities include the internal ASPECT User Forums (annual) and the external RCOF meetings, where users' feedback on the information presented and future potential developments should be sought. To ease the preparation of suitable materials for the user-targeted activities, the 'User Engagement Committee' has been established, with at least one representative from each ASPECT WP. This representative is in charge of ensuring the proper information flow among the different WPs.

Information about the Super Users' requirements will be also be delivered at these points in time through the relevant milestones and deliverables:

- *June 2023:* [Rapid assessment of climate information user needs \(D5.1\)](#)
- *January 2024:* Quantitative survey of climate sensitive organisations in Europe ([M18 - UF slides](#))
- *December 2024:* Review of participation in RCOF events and engagement with National Met Services, summarise progress to date and ongoing strategy ([milestone 26](#))
- *February 2025:* Analysis of how climate information can help organisations prepare for physical changes of a changing climate ([D5.3](#))

4. Good practice for the smooth development of the project

To avoid misunderstandings among project partners, work as efficiently as possible, and minimise user's fatigue, the following recommendations are provided in the context of ASPECT:

- **Respect the timings of the case study development:** the co-production of climate services with Super Users is a process that takes time and that needs multiple back and forth (timings defined by project milestones and deliverables). This is part of the research process in transdisciplinary co-production and the outcomes of this process constitute scientific results that partners working in co-production of climate services will aim to publish. It is important to take this into account when planning your publications.
- **Keep the information flow alive and coordinated:** always inform case study leads if you plan to work on developments for a particular case study and communicate the advancements to the WP4 case study lead in a transparent and open way. WP leads will be responsible for ensuring that partners add the work they are doing to the [table for the coordination of ASPECT activities](#), which contains information on who works on what, to avoid overlaps. Do not reach out to users with preliminary results (including conference presentations) without agreeing with case study leads first how and when is best to do this. This is important for the project to deliver a clear message to the users.
- **Consider intellectual property aspects:** If your work builds on project technical and non-technical developments made by other ASPECT partners, please consider co-authorship of the relevant persons on public project outcomes following traditional scientific practice.
- **Engage in user-focused project activities:** various project activities provide the ground for discussing user needs, including Super Users and a wider pool of stakeholders, and matching these needs with technical project developments (e.g. case study dedicated meetings, WP4 and 5 meetings, User Forums, User Engagement Committee meetings). WPs 1-3 and WP6 are encouraged to join these meetings so their concerns can be addressed and information can be exchanged.